

PROJECT REPORT ON GREEN HOUSE WITH SUSTANABLE ENERGY SYSTEM

BY

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Project Report on

Green House with Sustainable Energy System using PV Cell

Green House with sustainable energy system

Photovoltaic Cell (Type -1)

Photovoltaic Cell (Type-II)

```

function Ipv = fcn(u)
% This block supports an embeddable subset of the MATLAB language.
% See the help menu for details.
    TaC=u(1); Suns=u(2); Va=u(3); Ia=0;

    if Va<0
        Va=0
    end

    k=1.38e-23;
    q=1.60e-19;

    A=1.2; Vg=1.12; Ns=36;

    T1=273+25;
    Voc_T1=21.06/Ns;
    Isc_T1=3.80;

    T2=273+75;
    Voc_T2=17.05/Ns;
    Isc_T2=3.92;

    TaK=273+TaC;
    TrK=273+25;

    Iph_T1=Isc_T1*Suns;
    a=(Isc_T2-Isc_T1)/Isc_T1*1/(T2-T1);
    %//a=(Isc_T2-Isc_T1)/(T2-T1);
    Iph=Iph_T1*(1+a*(TaK-T1));

    Vt_T1=k*T1/q;
    Ir_T1=Isc_T1/(exp(Voc_T1/(A*Vt_T1))-1);
    Ir_T2=Isc_T2/(exp(Voc_T2/(A*Vt_T1))-1);

    b=Vg*q/(A*k);
    Ir=Ir_T1*((TaK/T1)^(3/A))*exp(-b*(1/TaK-1/T1));

    X2v=(Ir_T1/(A*Vt_T1))*exp(Voc_T1/(A*Vt_T1));
    dVdI_Voc=-1.15/Ns/2;
    Rs=-dVdI_Voc-1/X2v;

    Vt_Ta=A*k*TaK/q;

    Vc=Va/Ns;
    A1=Iph-Ia-Ir*(exp((Vc+Ia*Rs)/Vt_Ta)-1);
    A2=-1-Ir*(exp((Vc+Ia*Rs)/Vt_Ta)-1)*(Rs/Vt_Ta);
    Ia=Ia-A1/A2;

    %if (Ia<0)
    %    Ia=0.0001
    %end

```

Ipv=Ia;

Electrolysis

Hydrogen Storage Tank

Tsurrounding

Controller 1

Controller 2

Fuel cell

Dynamic model of the Fuel Cell.

House

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1. Fuel cell

A **fuel cell** is an electrochemical conversion device. It produces electricity from fuel (on the anode side) and an oxidant (on the cathode side), which react in the presence of an electrolyte. The reactants flow into the cell, and the reaction products flow out of it, while the electrolyte remains within it. Fuel cells can operate virtually continuously as long as the necessary flows are maintained.

Fuel cells are different from electrochemical cell batteries in that they consume reactant from an external source, which must be replenished -- a thermodynamically open system. By contrast batteries store electrical energy chemically and hence represent a thermodynamically closed system.

Many combinations of fuel and oxidant are possible. A hydrogen cell uses hydrogen as fuel and oxygen (usually from air) as oxidant. Other fuels include hydrocarbons and alcohols. Other oxidants include chlorine and chlorine dioxide.

Figure 1. Direct-methanol fuel cell. The actual fuel cell stack is the layered bi-cubic structure in the center of the image

1.1 Fuel cell design

A fuel cell works by catalysis, separating the component electrons and protons of the reactant fuel, and forcing the electrons to travel through a circuit, hence converting them to electrical power. The catalyst typically comprises a platinum group metal or alloy. Another catalytic process puts the electrons back in, combining them with the protons and oxidant to form waste products (typically simple compounds like water and carbon dioxide).

A typical fuel cell produces a voltage from 0.6 V to 0.7 V at full rated load. Voltage decreases as current increases, due to several factors:

- Activation loss
- Ohmic loss (voltage drop due to resistance of the cell components and interconnects)
- Mass transport loss (depletion of reactants at catalyst sites under high loads, causing rapid loss of voltage)

To deliver the desired amount of energy, the fuel cells can be combined in series and parallel circuits, where series yield higher voltage, and parallel allows a stronger current to be drawn. Such a design is called a *fuel cell stack*. Further, the cell surface area can be increased, to allow stronger current from each cell.

1.2 History

The principle of the fuel cell was discovered by German scientist Christian Friedrich Schönbein in 1838 and published in one of the scientific magazines of the time. Based on this work, the first fuel cell was demonstrated by Welsh scientist and barrister Sir William Robert Grove in the February 1839 edition of the *Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science* and later sketched, in 1842, in the same journal. The fuel cell he made used similar materials to today's phosphoric-acid fuel cell.

Figure 3. Sketch of William Grove's 1839 fuel cell

In 1955, W. Thomas Grubb, a chemist working for the General Electric Company (GE), further modified the original fuel cell design by using a sulphonated polystyrene ion-exchange membrane as the electrolyte. Three years later another GE chemist, Leonard Niedrach, devised a way of depositing platinum onto the membrane, which served as catalyst for the necessary hydrogen oxidation and oxygen reduction reactions. This became known as the 'Grubb-Niedrach fuel cell'. GE went on to develop this technology with NASA and McDonnell Aircraft, leading to its use during Project Gemini. This was the first commercial use of a fuel cell. It wasn't until 1959 that British engineer Francis Thomas Bacon successfully developed a 5 kW stationary fuel cell. In 1959, a team led by Harry Ihrig built a 15 kW fuel cell tractor for Allis-Chalmers which was demonstrated across the US at state fairs. This system used potassium hydroxide as the electrolyte and compressed hydrogen and oxygen as the reactants. Later in 1959, Bacon and his colleagues demonstrated a practical five-kilowatt unit capable of powering a welding machine. In the 1960s, Pratt and Whitney licensed Bacon's U.S. patents for use in the U.S. space program to supply electricity and drinking water (hydrogen and oxygen being readily available from the spacecraft tanks).

1.3 Proton exchange fuel cells

In the archetypal hydrogen–oxygen proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) design, a proton-conducting polymer membrane, (the electrolyte), separates the anode and cathode sides. This was called a "solid polymer electrolyte fuel cell" (SPEFC) in the early 1970s, before the proton exchange mechanism was well-understood.

On the anode side, hydrogen diffuses to the anode catalyst where it later dissociates into protons and electrons. These protons often react with oxidants causing them to become what is commonly referred to as multi-facilitated proton membranes (MFPM). The protons are conducted through the membrane to the cathode, but the electrons are forced to travel in an external circuit (supplying power) because the membrane is electrically insulating. On the cathode catalyst, oxygen molecules react with the electrons (which have traveled through the external circuit) and protons to form water — in this example, the only waste product, either liquid or vapor.

In addition to this pure hydrogen type, there are hydrocarbon fuels for fuel cells, including diesel, methanol (*see: direct-methanol fuel cells and indirect methanol fuel cells*) and chemical hydrides. The waste products with these types of fuel are carbon dioxide and water.

Proton exchange membrane fuel cell

Figure 2. Construction of a high temperature PEMFC: Bipolar plate as electrode with in-milled gas channel structure, fabricated from conductive plastics (enhanced with carbon nano tubes for more conductivity); Porous carbon papers; reactive layer, usually on the polymer membrane applied; polymer membrane.

The materials used in fuel cells differ by type. In a typical membrane electrode assembly (MEA), the electrode–bipolar plates are usually made of metal, nickel or carbon nanotubes, and are coated with a catalyst (like platinum, nano iron powders or palladium) for higher efficiency. Carbon paper separates them from the electrolyte. The electrolyte could be ceramic or a membrane.

Figure 3. Condensation of water produced by a PEMFC on the air channel wall. The gold wire around the cell ensures the collection of electric current.

1.4 Oxygen ion exchange fuel cells

In a solid oxide fuel cell design, the anode and cathode are separated by an electrolyte that is conductive to oxygen ions but non-conductive to electrons. The electrolyte is typically made from zirconia doped with yttria.

On the cathode side, oxygen catalytically reacts with a supply of electrons to become oxygen ions, which diffuse through the electrolyte to the anode side. On the anode side, the oxygen ions react with hydrogen to form water and free electrons. A load connected externally between the anode and cathode completes the electrical circuit.

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) are the most efficient type of fuel cell, and also the most fuel-flexible. That is, they can directly utilize a wide variety of commonly-available fuels, including natural gas, biogas, ethanol, methanol, hydrogen, carbon monoxide, and synthesis gas produced from coal or natural gas, without the thorough and extensive purification required for low-temperature fuel cells.

1.5 Types of fuel cells

Fuel Name	Cell	Electrolyte	Qualified Power (W)	Working Temperature (°C)	Electrical efficiency	Status	Cost per Watt
Metal hydride fuel cell		Aqueous alkaline solution (e.g. potassium hydroxide)		above -20 (50% P_{peak} @ 0°C)		Commercial/Research	
Electro-galvanic fuel cell		Aqueous alkaline solution (e.g., potassium hydroxide)		under 40		Commercial/Research	
Direct formic acid fuel cell (DFAFC)		Polymer membrane (ionomer)	to 50 W	under 40		Commercial/Research	

Zinc-air battery	Aqueous alkaline solution (e.g., potassium hydroxide)		under 40		Mass production
Microbial fuel cell	Polymer membrane or humic acid		under 40		Research
Upflow microbial fuel cell (UMFC)			under 40		Research
Regenerative fuel cell	Polymer membrane (ionomer)		under 50		Commercial/Research
Direct borohydride fuel cell	Aqueous alkaline solution (e.g., sodium hydroxide)		70		Commercial
Alkaline fuel cell	Aqueous alkaline solution (e.g., potassium hydroxide)	10 kW to 100 kW	under 80	Cell: 60–70% System: 62%	Commercial/Research
Direct methanol fuel cell	Polymer membrane (ionomer)	100 kW to 1 MW	90–120	Cell: 20–30% System: 10–20%	Commercial/Research
Reformed	Polymer	5 W to 100	(Reformer)250	Cell: 50–	Commercial/Research

methanol-fuel cell	membrane (ionomer)	kW	-300 (PBI)125-200	60% System: 25-40%	ch	
Direct-ethanol fuel cell	Polymer membrane (ionomer)	up to 140 mW/cm ²	above 25 ? 90-120		Research	
Direct formic acid fuel cell	Polymer membrane (ionomer)		25+		Research	
Proton exchange membrane fuel cell	Polymer membrane (ionomer) (e.g., Nafion or Polybenzimidazole fiber)	100 W to 500 kW	(Nafion)50-120 (PBI)125-220	Cell: 50-70% System: 30-50%	Commercial/Research	
RFC Redox	Liquid electrolytes with shuttle redox & polymer membrane (Ionomer)	1 kW to 10 MW			Research	
Phosphoric acid fuel cell	Molten phosphoric acid (H ₃ PO ₄)	up to 10 MW	150-200	Cell: 55% System: 40% Co-Gen: 90%	Commercial/Research	\$4-\$4.50 per watt
Molten carbonate fuel cell	Molten alkaline carbonate (e.g., sodium bicarbonate NaHCO ₃)	100 MW	600-650	Cell: 55% System: 47%	Commercial/Research	

Tubular solid oxide fuel cell (TSOFC)	O ²⁻ -conducting ceramic oxide (e.g., zirconium dioxide, ZrO ₂)	up to 100 MW	850-1100	Cell: 60–65% System: 55–60%	Commercial/Research
Protonic ceramic fuel cell	H ⁺ -conducting ceramic oxide		700		Research
Direct carbon fuel cell	Several different		700-850	Cell: 80% System: 70%	Commercial/Research
Planar Solid oxide fuel cell	O ²⁻ -conducting ceramic oxide (e.g., zirconium dioxide, ZrO ₂ Lanthanum Nickel Oxide La ₂ XO ₄ , X= Ni, Co, Cu.)	up to 100 MW	850-1100	Cell: 60–65% System: 55–60%	Commercial/Research

1.6 Efficiency

The efficiency of a fuel cell is dependent on the amount of power drawn from it. Drawing more power means drawing more current which increases the losses in the fuel cell. As a general rule, the more power (current) drawn the lower the efficiency. Most losses manifest themselves as a voltage drop in the cell, so the efficiency of a cell is almost proportional to its voltage. For this reason, it is common to show graphs of voltage versus current (so-called polarization curves) for fuel cells. A typical cell running at 0.7 V has an efficiency of about 50%, meaning that 50% of the energy content of the hydrogen is converted into electrical energy; the remaining 50% will be converted into heat. (Depending on the fuel cell system design, some fuel might leave the system unreacted, constituting an additional loss.)

For a hydrogen cell operating at standard conditions with no reactant leaks, the efficiency is equal to the cell voltage divided by 1.48 V, based on the enthalpy, or heating value, of the reaction. For the same cell, the second law efficiency is equal to cell voltage divided by 1.23 V. (This voltage varies with fuel used, and quality and temperature of the cell.) The difference between these numbers represents the difference between the reaction's enthalpy and Gibbs free

energy. This difference always appears as heat, along with any losses in electrical conversion efficiency.

Fuel cells do not operate on a thermal cycle. As such, they are not constrained, as combustion engines are, in the same way by thermodynamic limits, such as Carnot cycle efficiency. At times this is misrepresented by saying that fuel cells are exempt from the laws of thermodynamics, because most people think of thermodynamics in terms of combustion processes (enthalpy of formation). The laws of thermodynamics also hold for chemical processes (Gibbs free energy) like fuel cells, but the maximum theoretical efficiency is higher (83% efficient at 298K) than the Otto cycle thermal efficiency (60% for compression ratio of 10 and specific heat ratio of 1.4). Comparing limits imposed by thermodynamics is not a good predictor of practically achievable efficiencies. Also, if propulsion is the goal, electrical output of the fuel cell has to still be converted into mechanical power with the corresponding inefficiency. In reference to the exemption claim, the correct claim is that the "limitations imposed by the second law of thermodynamics on the operation of fuel cells are much less severe than the limitations imposed on conventional energy conversion systems". Consequently, they can have very high efficiencies in converting chemical energy to electrical energy, especially when they are operated at low power density, and using pure hydrogen and oxygen as reactants.

1.7 Suggested applications

- Base load power plants
- Electric and hybrid vehicles.
- Auxiliary power
- Off-grid power supply
- Notebook computers for applications where AC charging may not be available for weeks at a time.
- Portable charging docks for small electronics (e.g. a belt clip that charges your cell phone or PDA).
- Smart phones with high power consumption due to large displays and additional features like GPS might be equipped with micro fuel cells.

1.8 Hydrogen transportation and refueling

The first public hydrogen refueling station was opened in Reykjavík, Iceland in April 2003. This station serves three buses built by DaimlerChrysler that are in service in the public transport net of Reykjavík. The station produces the hydrogen it needs by itself, with an electrolyzing unit (produced by Norsk Hydro), and does not need refilling: all that enters is electricity and water. Royal Dutch Shell is also a partner in the project. The station has no roof, in order to allow any leaked hydrogen to escape to the atmosphere.

Figure 4. Toyota FCHV PEM FC fuel cell vehicle

The GM 1966 Electro van was the automotive industry's first attempt at an automobile powered by a hydrogen fuel cell. The Electro van, which weighed more than twice as much as a normal van, could travel up to 70mph for 30 seconds.

The 2001 Chrysler Natrium used its own on-board hydrogen processor. It produces hydrogen for the fuel cell by reacting sodium borohydride fuel with Borax, both of which Chrysler claimed were naturally occurring in great quantity in the United States. The hydrogen produces electric power in the fuel cell for near-silent operation and a range of 300 miles without impinging on passenger space. Chrysler also developed vehicles which separated hydrogen from gasoline in the vehicle, the purpose being to reduce emissions without relying on a nonexistent hydrogen infrastructure and to avoid large storage tanks.

In 2003 President George Bush proposed what is called the Hydrogen Fuel Initiative (HFI), which was later implemented by legislation through the 2005 Energy Policy Act and the 2006 Advanced Energy Initiative. These aim at further developing hydrogen fuel cells and its infrastructure technologies with the ultimate goal to produce fuel cell vehicles that are both practical and cost-effective by 2020. Thus far the United States has contributed 1 billion dollars to this project.

In 2005 the British firm Intelligent Energy produced the first ever working hydrogen run motorcycle called the ENV (Emission Neutral Vehicle). The motorcycle holds enough fuel to run for four hours, and to travel 100 miles in an urban area, at a top speed of 50 miles per hour. In 2004 Honda developed a fuel-cell motorcycle which utilized the Honda FC Stack.

There are numerous prototype or production cars and buses based on fuel cell technology being researched or manufactured. Research is ongoing at a variety of motor car manufacturers. Honda has released a hydrogen vehicle, the FCX Clarity earlier in 2008. Meanwhile there exist also other examples of bikes and bicycles with a hydrogen fuel cell engine.

Figure 5.A hydrogen fuel cell public bus accelerating at traffic lights in Perth, Western Australia

Type 212 submarines use fuel cells to remain submerged for weeks without the need to surface.

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2. Solar Cell

A **solar cell** or **photovoltaic cell** is a device that converts sunlight directly into electricity by the **photovoltaic effect**. Sometimes the term *solar cell* is reserved for devices intended specifically to capture energy from sunlight, while the term *photovoltaic cell* is used when the light source is unspecified. Assemblies of cells are used to make solar panels, solar modules, or photovoltaic arrays. Photovoltaic is the field of technology and research related to the application of solar cells in producing electricity for practical use. The energy generated this way is an example of solar energy (also called *solar power*).

Figure 1. Solar Cell

2.1 Timeline of Solar Energy

The term "photovoltaic" comes from the Greek $\phi\upsilon\lambda\omicron\varsigma$ (*phōs*) meaning "light", and "voltaic", meaning electric, from the name of the Italian physicist Volta, after whom a unit of electrical potential, the volt, is named. The term "photo-voltaic" has been in use in English since 1849.

The photovoltaic effect was first recognized in 1839 by French physicist A.E. Becquerel. However, it was not until 1883 that the first solar cell was built, by Charles Fritts, who coated the Semiconductor selenium with an extremely thin layer of gold to form the junctions. The device was only around 1% efficient. Sven Ason Berglund had a number of patents concerning methods of increasing the capacity of these cells. Russell Ohl patented the modern junction semiconductor solar cell in 1946, which was discovered while working on the series of advances that would lead to the transistor.

The modern age of solar power technology arrived in 1954 when Bell Laboratories, experimenting with semiconductors, accidentally found that silicon doped with certain impurities was very sensitive to light. Daryl Chapin, with Bell Labs colleagues Calvin Fuller and Gerald Pearson, invented the first practical device for converting sunlight into useful electrical power. This resulted in the production of the first practical solar cells with a sunlight energy conversion efficiency of around 6 percent. The solar battery was first demonstrated on April 25, 1954. The first spacecraft to use solar panels was the US satellite Vanguard 1, launched in March 1958 with solar cells made by Hoffman Electronics. This milestone created interest in producing and launching a geostationary communications satellite, in which solar energy would provide a viable power supply. This was a crucial development which stimulated funding from several governments into research for improved solar cells.

In 1970 the first highly effective GaAs heterostructure solar cells were created by Zhores Alferov and his team in the USSR. Metal Organic Chemical Vapor Deposition (MOCVD, or OMCVD) production equipment was not developed until the early 1980s, limiting the ability of companies to manufacture the GaAs solar cell. In the United States, the first 17% efficient air mass zero

(AM0) single-junction GaAs solar cells were manufactured in production quantities in 1988 by Applied Solar Energy Corporation (ASEC). The "dual junction" cell was accidentally produced in quantity by ASEC in 1989 as a result of the change from GaAs on GaAs substrates to GaAs on Germanium (Ge) substrates. The accidental doping of Ge with the GaAs buffer layer created higher open circuit voltages, demonstrating the potential of using the Ge substrate as another cell. As GaAs single-junction cells topped 19% AM0 production efficiency in 1993, ASEC developed the first dual junction cells for spacecraft use in the United States, with a starting efficiency of approximately 20%. These cells did not utilize the Ge as a second cell, but used another GaAs-based cell with different doping. Eventually GaAs dual junction cells reached production efficiencies of about 22%. Triple Junction solar cells began with AM0 efficiencies of approximately 24% in 2000, 26% in 2002, 28% in 2005, and in 2007 have evolved to a 30% AM0 production efficiency, currently in qualification.

Recent world record claims of efficiency for multiple junction solar cells are discussed in the Records section.

2.2 Three generations of solar cells

Solar Cells are classified into three generations which indicates the order of which each became important. At present there is concurrent research into all three generations while the first generation technologies are most highly represented in commercial production, accounting for 89.6% of 2007 production.

2.2.1 First Generation

First generation cells consist of large-area, high quality and single junction devices. First Generation technologies involve high energy and labor inputs which prevent any significant progress in reducing production costs. Single junction silicon devices are approaching the theoretical limiting efficiency of 33% and achieve cost parity with fossil fuel energy generation after a payback period of 5–7 years.

2.2.2 Second Generation

Second generation materials have been developed to address energy requirements and production costs of solar cells. Alternative manufacturing techniques such as vapor deposition, electroplating, and use of Ultrasonic Nozzles are advantageous as they reduce high temperature processing significantly.

The most successful second generation materials have been cadmium telluride (CdTe), copper indium gallium selenide, amorphous silicon and micro morphous silicon. These materials are applied in a thin film to a supporting substrate such as glass or ceramics reducing material mass and therefore costs. These technologies do hold promise of higher conversion efficiencies, particularly CIGS-CIS, DSC and CdTe offers significantly cheaper production costs.

Among major manufacturers there is certainly a trend toward second generation technologies; however commercialization of these technologies has proven difficult. In 2007 First Solar

produced 200 MW of CdTe solar cells making it the fifth largest producer of solar cells in 2007 and the first ever to reach the top 10 from production of second generation technologies alone.

2.2.3 Third Generation

Third generation technologies aim to enhance poor electrical performance of second generation (thin-film technologies) while maintaining very low production costs.

Current research is targeting conversion efficiencies of 30-60% while retaining low cost materials and manufacturing techniques. They can exceed the theoretical solar conversion efficiency limit for a single energy threshold material that was calculated in 1961 by Shockley and Queisser as 31% under 1 sun illumination and 40.8% under maximal concentration of sunlight (46,200 suns, which makes the latter limit more difficult to approach than the former).

There are a few approaches to achieving these high efficiencies including the use of Multi junction photovoltaic cells, concentration of the incident spectrum, and the use of thermal generation by UV light to enhance voltage or carrier collection, or the use of the infrared spectrum for night-time operation.

2.3 High efficiency cells

High efficiency solar cells are a class of **solar cell** that can generate electricity at higher efficiencies than conventional solar cells. While high efficiency solar cells are more efficient in terms of electrical output per incident energy (watt/watt), much of the industry is focused on the most cost efficient technologies, i.e. cost-per-watt. Many businesses and academics are focused on increasing the electrical efficiency of cells, and much development is focused on high efficiency solar cells.

2.3.1 Multiple junction solar cells

The record for multiple junction solar cells is disputed. Teams led by the University of Delaware, the Fraunhofer Institute, and NREL all claim the world record title at 42.8, 41.1, and 40.8 percent, respectively. NREL claims that the other implementations have not been put under standardized tests and, in the case of the University of Delaware project, represents only hypothetical efficiencies of a panel that has not been fully assembled. NREL claims it is one of only three laboratories in the world capable of conducting valid tests, although the Fraunhofer Institute is among those three facilities.

2.3.2 Thin film solar cells

In 2002, the highest reported efficiency for solar cells based on thin films of CdTe is 18%, which was achieved by research at Sheffield Hallam University, although this has not been confirmed by an external test laboratory.

The US national renewable energy research facility NREL achieved an efficiency of 19.9% for the solar cells based on copper indium gallium selenide thin films, also known as CIGS. These

CIGS films have been grown by physical vapour deposition in a three-stage co-evaporation process. In this process In, Ga and Se are evaporated in the first step; in the second step it is followed by Cu and Se co-evaporation and in the last step terminated by In, Ga and Se evaporation again.

2.4 Applications and implementations

Figure 2. Polycrystalline cells laminated to backing material in a PV module

Figure 3. Polycrystalline PV cells

Solar cells are often electrically connected and encapsulated as a **module**. PV modules often have a sheet of glass on the front (sun up) side, allowing light to pass while protecting the semiconductor wafers from the elements (rain, hail, etc.). Solar cells are also usually connected in series in modules, creating an additive voltage. Connecting cells in parallel will yield a higher current. Modules are then interconnected, in series or parallel, or both, to create an **array** with the desired peak DC voltage and current.

The power output of a solar array is measured in watts or kilowatts. In order to calculate the typical energy needs of the application, a measurement in watt-hours, kilowatt-hours or kilowatt-hours per day is often used. A common rule of thumb is that average power is equal to 20% of peak power, so that each peak kilowatt of solar array output power corresponds to energy production of 4.8 kWh per day ($24 \text{ hours} \times 1 \text{ kW} \times 20\% = 4.8 \text{ kWh}$)

To make practical use of the solar-generated energy, the electricity is most often fed into the electricity grid using inverters (grid-connected PV systems); in standalone systems, batteries are used to store the energy that is not needed immediately.

Solar cells can also be applied to other electronic devices to make itself power sustainable in the sun. There are solar cell phone chargers, solar bike light and solar camping lanterns that people can adopt for daily use.

2.5 Theory

2.5.1 Simple explanation

1. Photons in sunlight hit the solar panel and are absorbed by semiconducting materials, such as silicon.
2. Electrons (negatively charged) are knocked loose from their atoms, allowing them to flow through the material to produce electricity. Due to the special composition of solar cells, the electrons are only allowed to move in a single direction. The complementary positive charges that are also created (like bubbles) are called holes and flow in the direction opposite of the electrons in a silicon solar panel.
3. An array of solar cells converts solar energy into a usable amount of direct current (DC) electricity.

2.5.2 Photo generation of charge carriers

When a photon hits a piece of silicon, one of three things can happen:

1. The photon can pass straight through the silicon — this (generally) happens for lower energy photons,
2. The photon can reflect off the surface,
3. The photon can be absorbed by the silicon, if the photon energy is higher than the silicon band gap value. This generates an electron-hole pair and sometimes heat, depending on the band structure.

When a photon is absorbed, its energy is given to an electron in the crystal lattice. Usually this electron is in the valence band, and is tightly bound in covalent bonds between neighboring atoms, and hence unable to move far. The energy given to it by the photon "excites" it into the conduction band, where it is free to move around within the semiconductor. The covalent bond that the electron was previously a part of now has one fewer electron — this is known as a hole. The presence of a missing covalent bond allows the bonded electrons of neighboring atoms to move into the "hole," leaving another hole behind, and in this way a hole can move through the lattice. Thus, it can be said that photons absorbed in the semiconductor create mobile electron-hole pairs.

A photon need only have greater energy than that of the band gap in order to excite an electron from the valence band into the conduction band. However, the solar frequency spectrum approximates a black body spectrum at ~6000 K, and as such, much of the solar radiation reaching the Earth is composed of photons with energies greater than the band gap of silicon. These higher energy photons will be absorbed by the solar cell, but the difference in energy between these photons and the silicon band gap is converted into heat (via lattice vibrations — called phonons) rather than into usable electrical energy.

2.5.3 Charge carrier separation

There are two main modes for charge carrier separation in a solar cell:

1. **Drift** of carriers, driven by an electrostatic field established across the device
2. **Diffusion** of carriers from zones of high carrier concentration to zones of low carrier concentration (following a gradient of electrochemical potential).

In the widely used p-n junction solar cells, the dominant mode of charge carrier separation is by drift. However, in non-p-n-junction solar cells (typical of the third generation solar cell research such as dye and polymer solar cells), a general electrostatic field has been confirmed to be absent, and the dominant mode of separation is via charge carrier diffusion.

2.5.4 The p-n junction

The most commonly known solar cell is configured as a large-area p-n junction made from silicon. As a simplification, one can imagine bringing a layer of n-type silicon into direct contact with a layer of p-type silicon. In practice, p-n junctions of silicon solar cells are not made in this way, but rather, by diffusing an n-type dopant into one side of a p-type wafer (or vice versa).

If a piece of p-type silicon is placed in intimate contact with a piece of n-type silicon, then a diffusion of electrons occurs from the region of high electron concentration (the n-type side of the junction) into the region of low electron concentration (p-type side of the junction). When the electrons diffuse across the p-n junction, they recombine with holes on the p-type side. The diffusion of carriers does not happen indefinitely however, because of an electric field which is created by the imbalance of charge immediately on either side of the junction which this diffusion creates. The electric field established across the p-n junction creates a diode that promotes charge flow, known as drift current, that opposes and eventually balances out the diffusion of electron and holes. This region where electrons and holes have diffused across the junction is called the depletion region because it no longer contains any mobile charge carriers. It is also known as the "space charge region".

2.5.5 Connection to an external load

Ohmic metal-semiconductor contacts are made to both the n-type and p-type sides of the solar cell, and the electrodes connected to an external load. Electrons that are created on the n-type side, or have been "collected" by the junction and swept onto the n-type side, may travel through the wire, power the load, and continue through the wire until they reach the p-type semiconductor-metal contact. Here, they recombine with a hole that was either created as an electron-hole pair on the p-type side of the solar cell, or are swept across the junction from the n-type side after being created there.

The voltage measured is equal to the difference in the quasi Fermi levels of the minority carriers i.e. electrons in the p-type portion, and holes in the n-type portion.

2.5.6 Equivalent circuit of a solar cell

Figure4. The equivalent circuit of a solar cell

Figure5. The schematic symbol of a solar cell

To understand the electronic behavior of a solar cell, it is useful to create a model which is electrically equivalent, and is based on discrete electrical components whose behavior is well known. An ideal solar cell may be modeled by a current source in parallel with a diode; in practice no solar cell is ideal, so a shunt resistance and a series resistance component are added to the model. The resulting equivalent circuit of a solar cell is shown in the figure.

2.5.7 Characteristic equation

From the equivalent circuit it is evident that the current produced by the solar cell is equal to that produced by the current source, minus that which flows through the diode, minus that which flows through the shunt resistor:

$$I = I_L - I_D - I_{SH}$$

Where

- I = output current (amperes)
- I_L = photo generated current (amperes)
- I_D = diode current (amperes)
- I_{SH} = shunt current (amperes)

The current flowing through these elements is governed by the voltage across them:

$$V_j = V + IR_S$$

Where

- V_j = voltage across both diode and resistor R_{SH} (volts)
- V = voltage across the output terminals (volts)
- I = output current (amperes)
- R_S = series resistance (Ω)

By the Shockley diode equation, the current diverted through the diode is:

$$I_D = I_0 \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{qV_j}{nkT} \right] - 1 \right\}$$

Where

- I_0 = reverse saturation current (amperes)
- n = diode ideality factor (1 for an ideal diode)
- q = elementary charge
- k = Boltzmann's constant
- T = absolute temperature
- For silicon at 25°C, $kT/q \approx 0.0259$ volts.

By Ohm's law, the current diverted through the shunt resistor is:

$$I_{SH} = \frac{V_j}{R_{SH}}$$

Where

- R_{SH} = shunt resistance (Ω)

Substituting these into the first equation produces the characteristic equation of a solar cell, which relates solar cell parameters to the output current and voltage:

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{q(V + IR_S)}{nkT} \right] - 1 \right\} - \frac{V + IR_S}{R_{SH}}$$

An alternative derivation produces an equation similar in appearance, but with V on the left-hand side. The two alternatives are identities; that is, they yield precisely the same results.

In principle, given a particular operating voltage V the equation may be solved to determine the operating current I at that voltage. However, because the equation involves ' I ' on both sides in a transcendental function the equation has no general analytical solution. However, even without a solution it is physically instructive. Furthermore, it is easily solved using numerical methods. (A general analytical solution to the equation is possible using Lambert's W function, but since Lambert's W generally itself must be solved numerically this is a technicality.)

Since the parameters I_0 , n , R_S , and R_{SH} cannot be measured directly, the most common application of the characteristic equation is nonlinear regression to extract the values of these parameters on the basis of their combined effect on solar cell behavior.

2.5.8 Effect of physical size

The values of I_0 , R_S , and R_{SH} are dependent upon the physical size of the solar cell. In comparing otherwise identical cells, a cell with twice the surface area of another will, in principle, have double the I_0 because it has twice the junction area across which current can leak. It will also have half the R_S and R_{SH} because it has twice the cross-sectional area through which current can flow. For this reason, the characteristic equation is frequently written in terms of current density, or current produced per unit cell area:

$$J = J_L - J_0 \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{q(V + Jr_S)}{nkT} \right] - 1 \right\} - \frac{V + Jr_S}{r_{SH}}$$

Where

- J = current density (amperes/cm²)
- J_L = photo generated current density (amperes/cm²)
- J_0 = reverse saturation current density (amperes/cm²)
- r_S = specific series resistance (Ω -cm²)
- r_{SH} = specific shunt resistance (Ω -cm²)

This formulation has several advantages. One is that since cell characteristics are referenced to a common cross-sectional area they may be compared for cells of different physical dimensions. While this is of limited benefit in a manufacturing setting, where all cells tend to be the same size, it is useful in research and in comparing cells between manufacturers. Another advantage is that the density equation naturally scales the parameter values to similar orders of magnitude, which can make numerical extraction of them simpler and more accurate even with naive solution methods.

A practical limitation of this formulation is that as cell sizes shrink, certain parasitic effects grow in importance and can affect the extracted parameter values. For example, recombination and contamination of the junction tend to be greatest at the perimeter of the cell, so very small cells may exhibit higher values of J_0 or lower values of r_{SH} than larger cells that are otherwise identical. In such cases, comparisons between cells must be made cautiously and with these effects in mind.

2.5.9 Cell temperature

Temperature affects the characteristic equation in two ways: directly, via T in the exponential term, and indirectly via its effect on I_0 . (Strictly speaking, temperature affects all of the terms, but these two far more significantly than the others.) While increasing T reduces the magnitude of the exponent in the characteristic equation, the value of I_0 increases in proportion to $\exp T$. The net effect is to reduce V_{OC} linearly with increasing temperature. The magnitude of this reduction is inversely proportional to V_{OC} ; that is, cells with higher values of V_{OC} suffer smaller reductions in voltage with increasing temperature. For most crystalline silicon solar cells the reduction is about 0.50%/°C, though the rate for the highest-efficiency crystalline silicon cells is around

0.35%/°C. By way of comparison, the rate for amorphous silicon solar cells is 0.20-0.30%/°C, depending on how the cell is made.

Figure 6. Effect of temperature on the current-voltage characteristics of a solar cell

The amount of photo generated current I_L increases slightly with increasing temperature because of an increase in the number of thermally generated carriers in the cell. This effect is slight, however: about 0.065%/°C for crystalline silicon cells and 0.09% for amorphous silicon cells.

The overall effect of temperature on cell efficiency can be computed using these factors in combination with the characteristic equation. However, since the change in voltage is much stronger than the change in current, the overall effect on efficiency tends to be similar to that on voltage. Most crystalline silicon solar cells decline in efficiency by 0.50%/°C and most amorphous cells decline by 0.15-0.25%/°C. The figure to the right shows I-V curves that might typically be seen for a crystalline silicon solar cell at various temperatures.

2.5.10 Series resistance

As series resistance increases, the voltage drop between the junction voltage and the terminal voltage becomes greater for the same flow of current. The result is that the current-controlled portion of the I-V curve begins to sag toward the origin, producing a significant decrease in the terminal voltage V and a slight reduction in I_{SC} . Very high values of R_S will also produce a significant reduction in I_{SC} ; in these regimes, series resistance dominates and the behavior of the solar cell resembles that of a resistor. These effects are shown for crystalline silicon solar cells in the I-V curves displayed in the figure to the right.

Figure 6. Effect of series resistance on the current-voltage characteristics of a solar cell

2.5.11 Shunt-resistance

As shunt resistance decreases, the flow of current diverted through the shunt resistor increases for a given level of junction voltage. The result is that the voltage-controlled portion of the I-V curve begins to sag toward the origin, producing a significant decrease in the terminal current I and a slight reduction in V_{OC} . Very low values of R_{SH} will produce a significant reduction in V_{OC} . Much as in the case of a high series resistance, a badly shunted solar cell will take on operating characteristics similar to those of a resistor. These effects are shown for crystalline silicon solar cells in the I-V curves displayed in the figure to the right.

Figure 7. Effect of shunt resistance on the current-voltage characteristics of a solar cell

2.5.12 Reverse saturation current

If one assumes infinite shunt resistance, the characteristic equation can be solved for V_{OC} :

$$V_{OC} = \frac{kT}{q} \ln \left(\frac{I_{SC}}{I_0} + 1 \right).$$

Thus, an increase in I_0 produces a reduction in V_{OC} proportional to the inverse of the logarithm of the increase. This explains mathematically the reason for the reduction in V_{OC} that accompanies increases in temperature described above. The effect of reverse saturation current on the I-V curve of a crystalline silicon solar cell is shown in the figure. Physically, reverse saturation current is a measure of the "leakage" of carriers across the p-n junction in reverse bias.

This leakage is a result of carrier recombination in the neutral regions on either side of the junction.

Figure 8. Effect of reverse saturation current on the current-voltage characteristics of a solar cell

2.5.13 Ideality factor

The ideality factor (also called the emissivity factor) is a fitting parameter that describes how closely the diode's behavior matches that predicted by theory, which assumes the p-n junction of the diode is an infinite plane and no recombination occurs within the space-charge region. A perfect match to theory is indicated when $n = 1$. When recombination in the space-charge region dominates other recombination, however, $n = 2$. The effect of changing ideality factor independently of all other parameters is shown for a crystalline silicon solar cell in the I-V curves displayed in the figure to the right.

Figure 9. Effect of ideality factor on the current-voltage characteristics of a solar cell

Most solar cells, which are quite large compared to conventional diodes, well approximate an infinite plane and will usually exhibit near-ideal behavior under Standard Test Condition ($n \approx 1$). Under certain operating conditions, however, device operation may be dominated by recombination in the space-charge region. This is characterized by a significant increase in I_0 as well as an increase in ideality factor to $n \approx 2$. The latter tends to erode solar cell output voltage while the former acts to increase it. The net effect, therefore, is a combination of the increase in voltage shown for increasing n in the figure to the right and the decrease in voltage shown for increasing I_0 in the figure above. Typically, I_0 is the more significant factor and the result is a reduction in voltage.

2.6 Solar cell efficiency factors

A solar cell's *energy conversion efficiency* (η , "eta"), is the percentage of power converted (from absorbed light to electrical energy) and collected, when a solar cell is connected to an electrical circuit. This term is calculated using the ratio of the maximum power point, P_m , divided by the input light irradiance (E , in W/m^2) under standard test conditions (STC) and the *surface area* of the solar cell (A_c in m^2).

$$\eta = \frac{P_m}{E \times A_c}$$

Figure 10. Dust often accumulates on the glass of Solar Panels. Seen here as black dots.

STC specifies a temperature of 25°C and an irradiance of 1000 W/m² with an air mass 1.5 (AM1.5) spectrum. These correspond to the irradiance and spectrum of sunlight incident on a clear day upon a sun-facing 37°-tilted surface with the sun at an angle of 41.81° above the horizon. This condition approximately represents solar noon near the spring and autumn equinoxes in the continental United States with surface of the cell aimed directly at the sun. Thus, under these conditions a solar cell of 12% efficiency with a 100 cm² (0.01 m²) surface area can be expected to produce approximately 1.2 watts of power.

The losses of a solar cell may be broken down into reflectance losses, thermodynamic efficiency, recombination losses and resistive electrical loss. The overall efficiency is the product of each of these individual losses.

Due to the difficulty in measuring these parameters directly, other parameters are measured instead: Thermodynamic Efficiency, Quantum Efficiency, V_{OC} ratio, and Fill Factor. Reflectance losses are a portion of the Quantum Efficiency under "External Quantum Efficiency". Recombination losses make up a portion of the Quantum Efficiency, V_{OC} ratio, and Fill Factor. Resistive losses are predominantly categorized under Fill Factor, but also make up minor portions of the Quantum Efficiency, V_{OC} ratio.

2.7 Thermodynamic Efficiency Limit

Solar cells operate as quantum energy conversion devices, and are therefore subject to the "Thermodynamic Efficiency Limit". Photons with energy below the band gap of the absorber material cannot generate a hole-electron pair, and so their energy is not converted to useful output and only generates heat if absorbed. For photons with energy above the band gap energy, only a fraction of the energy above the band gap can be converted to useful output. When a photon of greater energy is absorbed, the excess energy above the band gap is converted to kinetic energy of the carrier combination. The excess kinetic energy is converted to heat through phonon interactions as the kinetic energy of the carriers slows to equilibrium velocity.

Solar cells with multiple band gap absorber materials are able to more efficiently convert the solar spectrum. By using multiple band gaps, the solar spectrum may be broken down into smaller bins where the thermodynamic efficiency limit is higher for each bin.

2.8 Quantum efficiency

As described above, when a photon is absorbed by a solar cell it can produce a pair of free charge carriers, i.e. an electron-hole pair. One of the carriers (the minority carrier) may then be able to reach the p-n junction and contribute to the current produced by the solar cell; such a carrier is said to be *collected*. Alternatively, the carrier may give up its energy and once again become bound to an atom within the solar cell *without being collected*; this process is then called *recombination* since one electron and one hole recombine and thereby annihilate the associated free charge. The carriers that recombine do *not contribute* to the generation of electrical current.

Quantum efficiency refers to the percentage of photons that are converted to electric current (i.e., collected carriers) when the cell is operated under short circuit conditions. *External* quantum

efficiency (EQE) is the fraction of *incident* photons that are converted to electrical current, while *internal* quantum efficiency (IQE) is the fraction of *absorbed* photons that are converted to electrical current. Mathematically, internal quantum efficiency is related to external quantum efficiency by the reflectance (R) and the transmittance (T) of the solar cell by $IQE = EQE / (1 - R - T)$. Please note that for a thick bulk Si solar cell T is approximately zero and is therefore in practical cases often neglected.

Quantum efficiency should not be confused with energy conversion efficiency, as it does not convey information about the fraction of power that is converted by the solar cell. Furthermore, quantum efficiency is most usefully expressed as a *spectral* measurement (that is, as a function of photon wavelength or energy). Since some wavelengths are absorbed more effectively than others in most semiconductors, spectral measurements of quantum efficiency can yield valuable information about which parts of a particular solar cell design are most in need of improvement. Spectral quantum efficiency measurements also allow determining important solar cell parameters such as the base diffusion length.

2.9 Maximum-power point

A solar cell may operate over a wide range of voltages (V) and currents (I). By increasing the resistive load on an irradiated cell continuously from zero (a *short circuit*) to a very high value (an *open circuit*) one can determine the maximum-power point, the point that maximizes $V \times I$; that is, the load for which the cell can deliver maximum electrical power at that level of irradiation. (The output power is zero in both the short circuit and open circuit extremes).

A high quality, mono crystalline silicon solar cell, at 25 °C cell temperature, may produce 0.60 volts open-circuit (Voc). The cell temperature in full sunlight, even with 25 °C air temperature, will probably be close to 45 °C, reducing the open-circuit voltage to 0.55 volts per cell. The voltage drops modestly, with this type of cell, until the short-circuit current is approached (Isc). Maximum power (with 45 °C cell temperature) is typically produced with 75% to 80% of the open-circuit voltage (0.43 volts in this case) and 90% of the short-circuit current. This output can be up to 70% of the Voc x Isc product. The short-circuit current (Isc) from a cell is nearly proportional to the illumination, while the open-circuit voltage (Voc) may drop only 10% with an 80% drop in illumination. Lower-quality cells have a more rapid drop in voltage with increasing current and could produce only 1/2 Voc at 1/2 Isc. The usable power output could thus drop from 70% of the Voc x Isc product to 50% or even as little as 25%. Vendors, who rate their solar cell "power" only as Voc x Isc, without giving load curves, can be seriously distorting their actual performance.

The maximum power point of a photovoltaic varies with incident illumination. For systems large enough to justify the extra expense, a maximum power point tracker tracks the instantaneous power by continually measuring the voltage and current (and hence, power transfer), and uses this information to dynamically adjust the load so the maximum power is *always* transferred, regardless of the variation in lighting.

2.10 Fill factor

Another defining term in the overall behavior of a solar cell is the *fill factor* (FF). This is the ratio of the *maximum power point* divided by the *open circuit voltage* (V_{oc}) and the *short circuit current* (I_{sc}):

$$FF = \frac{P_m}{V_{oc} \times I_{sc}} = \frac{\eta \times A_c \times E}{V_{oc} \times I_{sc}}.$$

The fill factor is directly affected by the values of the cells series and shunt resistance. Increasing the shunt resistance (R_{sh}) and decreasing the series resistance (R_s) will lead to higher fill factor, thus resulting in greater efficiency, and pushing the cells output power closer towards its theoretical maximum.

2.11 Comparison of energy conversion efficiencies

At this point, discussion of the different ways to calculate efficiency for space cells and terrestrial cells is necessary to alleviate confusion. In space, where there is no atmosphere, the spectrum of the sun is relatively unfiltered. However on earth with air filtering the incoming light the solar spectrum changes. To account for the spectral differences, a system was devised to calculate this filtering effect. Simply, the filtering effect ranges from Air Mass 0 (AM0) in space, to approximately Air Mass 1.5 on earth. Multiplying the spectral differences by the quantum efficiency of the solar cell in question will yield the efficiency of the device. For example, a Silicon solar cell in space might have an efficiency of 14% at AM0, but have an efficiency of 16% on earth at AM 1.5. Terrestrial efficiencies typically are greater than space efficiencies.

Solar cell efficiencies vary from 6% for amorphous silicon-based solar cells to 40.7% with multiple-junction research lab cells and 42.8% with multiple dies assembled into a hybrid package. Solar cell energy conversion efficiencies for commercially available *multi crystalline Si* solar cells are around 14-19%. The highest efficiency cells have not always been the most economical — for example a 30% efficient multi junction cell based on exotic materials such as gallium arsenide or indium selenide and produced in low volume might well cost one hundred times as much as an 8% efficient amorphous silicon cell in mass production, while only delivering about four times the electrical power.

However, there is a way to "boost" solar power. By increasing the light intensity, typically photo generated carriers are increased, resulting in increased efficiency by up to 15%. These so-called "concentrator systems" have only begun to become cost-competitive as a result of the development of high efficiency GaAs cells. The increase in intensity is typically accomplished by using concentrating optics. A typical concentrator system may use a light intensity 6-400 times the sun, and increase the efficiency of a one sun GaAs cell from 31% at AM 1.5 to 35%.

A common method used to express economic costs of electricity-generating systems is to calculate a price per delivered kilowatt-hour (kWh). The solar cell efficiency in combination with the available irradiation has a major influence on the costs, but generally speaking the overall system efficiency is important. Using the commercially available solar cells (as of 2006)

and system technology leads to system efficiencies between 5 and 19%. As of 2005, photovoltaic electricity generation costs ranged from ~0.60 US\$/kWh (0.50 €/kWh) (central Europe) down to ~0.30 US\$/kWh (0.25 €/kWh) in regions of high solar irradiation. This electricity is generally fed into the electrical grid on the customer's side of the meter. The cost can be compared to prevailing retail electric pricing (as of 2005), which varied from between 0.04 and 0.50 US\$/kWh worldwide. (Note: in addition to solar irradiance profiles, these costs/kwh calculations will vary depending on assumptions for years of useful life of a system. Most c-Si panels are warranted for 25 years and should see 35+ years of useful life.)

The chart illustrates the various commercial large-area module energy conversion efficiencies and the best laboratory efficiencies obtained for various materials and technologies.

Figure 11. Reported timeline of solar cell energy conversion efficiencies (from National Renewable Energy Laboratory (USA))

2.12 Watts peak

Since solar cell output power depends on multiple factors, such as the sun's incidence angle, for comparison purposes between different cells and panels, the measure of watts peak (Wp) is used. It is the output power under these conditions known as STC. The standard test conditions imply and insulation (solar irradiance) of 1000 W/m², a solar reference spectrum AM (air mass) of 1.5 and a cell temperature 25°C

2.13 Solar cells and energy payback

In the 1990s, when silicon cells were twice as thick, efficiencies were much lower than today and lifetimes were shorter, it may well have cost more energy to make a cell than it could generate in a lifetime. In the meantime, the technology has progressed significantly, and the energy payback time, defined as the recovery time required for generating the energy spent for manufacturing of the respective technical energy systems, of a modern photovoltaic module is typically from 1 to 4 years depending on the module type and location. Generally, thin film technologies - despite having comparatively low conversion efficiencies - achieve significantly shorter energy payback times than conventional systems (often < 1 year). With a typical lifetime of 20 to 30 years, this means that modern solar cells are net energy producers, i.e. they generate significantly more energy over their lifetime than the energy expended in producing them.

2.14 Light-absorbing materials

All solar cells require a *light absorbing material* contained within the cell structure to absorb photons and generate electrons via the *photovoltaic effect*. The materials used in solar cells tend to have the property of preferentially absorbing the wavelengths of solar light that reach the earth surface; however, some solar cells are optimized for light absorption beyond Earth's atmosphere as well. Light absorbing materials can often be used in *multiple physical configurations* to take advantage of different light absorption and charge separation mechanisms.

Photovoltaic panels are normally made of either silicon or thin-film cells:

Many currently available solar cells are configured as **bulk** materials that are subsequently cut into wafers and treated in a "top-down" method of synthesis (**silicon** being the most prevalent bulk material).

Other materials are configured as **thin-films** (inorganic layers, organic dyes, and organic polymers) that are deposited on **supporting substrates**, while a third group are configured as **nano crystals** and used as **quantum dots** (electron-confined nano particles) embedded in a supporting matrix in a "bottom-up" approach. Silicon remains the only material that is well-researched in both *bulk* (also called wafer-based) and *thin-film* configurations.

2.15 Bulk

These *bulk* technologies are often referred to as wafer-based manufacturing. In other words, in each of these approaches, self-supporting wafers between 180 to 240 micrometers thick are processed and then soldered together to form a solar cell module.

2.16 Crystalline silicon

Figure 12. Basic structure of a silicon based solar cell and its working mechanism.

By far, the most prevalent *bulk* material for solar cells is crystalline silicon (abbreviated as a group as *c-Si*), also known as "solar grade silicon". Bulk silicon is separated into multiple categories according to crystalline and crystal size in the resulting ingot, ribbon, or wafer.

1. *monocrystalline silicon* (*c-Si*): often made using the Czochralski process. Single-crystal wafer cells tend to be expensive, and because they are cut from cylindrical ingots, do not completely cover a square solar cell module without a substantial waste of refined silicon. Hence most *c-Si* panels have uncovered gaps at the four corners of the cells.

Ribbon silicon is a type of mono crystalline silicon: it is formed by drawing flat thin films from molten silicon and having a multi crystalline structure. These cells have lower efficiencies than poly-Si, but save on production costs due to a great reduction in silicon waste, as this approach does not require sawing from ingots.

2. *Poly- or multi crystalline silicon* (poly-Si or mc-Si): made from cast square ingots — large blocks of molten silicon carefully cooled and solidified. Poly-Si cells are less expensive to produce than single crystal silicon cells, but are less efficient. US DOE data shows that there were a higher number of multi crystalline sales than mono crystalline silicon sales.

2.17 Thin-films

The various *thin-film* technologies currently being developed reduce the amount (or mass) of **light absorbing material** required in creating a *solar cell*. This can lead to reduced processing costs from that of bulk materials (in the case of silicon thin films) but also tends to reduce *energy conversion efficiency* (average 7 to 10% efficiency), although many multi-layer thin films have efficiencies above those of bulk silicon wafers.

They have become popular compared to wafer silicon due to lower costs and advantages including flexibility, lighter weights, and ease of integration.

2.17.1 Cadmium telluride solar cell

A cadmium telluride solar cell is a solar cell based on cadmium telluride, an efficient light-absorbing material for thin-film cells. Compared to other thin-film materials, CdTe is easier to deposit and more suitable for large-scale production.

There has been much discussion of the toxicity of CdTe-based solar cells. The perception of the toxicity of CdTe is based on the toxicity of elemental cadmium, a heavy metal that is a cumulative poison. While the toxicity of CdTe is presently under debate, it has been shown that the release of cadmium to the atmosphere is impossible during normal operation of the cells and is unlikely during fires in residential roofs. Furthermore, a square meter of CdTe contains approximately the same amount of Cd as a single C cell Nickel-cadmium battery, in a more stable and less soluble form.

2.17.2 Copper-Indium Selenide

Possible combinations of (I, III, VI) elements in the periodic table that have photovoltaic effect

The materials based on CuInSe_2 that are of interest for photovoltaic applications include several elements from groups I, III and VI in the periodic table. These semiconductors are especially attractive for thin film solar cell application because of their high optical absorption coefficients and versatile optical and electrical characteristics which can in principle be manipulated and tuned for a specific need in a given device.

CIS is an abbreviation for general chalcopyrite films of copper indium selenide (CuInSe_2), CIGS mentioned below is a variation of CIS. CIS films (no Ga) achieved greater than 14% efficiency. However, manufacturing costs of CIS solar cells at present are high when compared with amorphous silicon solar cells but continuing work is leading to more cost-effective production processes. The first large-scale production of CIS modules was started in 2006 in Germany by

Wuerth Solar. Manufacturing techniques vary and include the use of Ultrasonic Nozzles for material deposition.

When gallium is substituted for some of the indium in CIS, the material is referred to as CIGS, or copper indium/gallium diselenide, a solid mixture of the semiconductors CuInSe_2 and CuGaSe_2 , often abbreviated by the chemical formula $\text{CuIn}_x\text{Ga}_{(1-x)}\text{Se}_2$. Unlike the conventional silicon based solar cell, which can be modelled as a simple p-n junction (see under semiconductor), these cells are best described by a more complex hetero junction model. The best efficiency of a thin-film solar cell as of March 2008 was 19.9% with CIGS absorber layer. Higher efficiencies (around 30%) can be obtained by using optics to concentrate the incident light or by using multi-junction tandem solar cells. The use of gallium increases the optical band gap of the CIGS layer as compared to pure CIS, thus increasing the open-circuit voltage, but decreasing the short circuit current. In another point of view, gallium is added to replace indium due to gallium's relative availability to indium. Approximately 70% of indium currently produced is used by the flat-screen monitor industry. However, the atomic ratio for Ga in the >19% efficient CIGS solar cells is ~7%, which corresponds to a band gap of ~1.15 eV. CIGS solar cells with higher Ga amounts have lower efficiency. For example CGS solar cells (which have a band gap of ~1.7eV have a record efficiency of 9.5% for pure CGS and 10.2% for surface-modified CGS. Some investors in solar technology worry that production of CIGS cells will be limited by the availability of indium. Producing 2 GW of CIGS cells (roughly the amount of silicon cells produced in 2006) would use about 10% of the indium produced in 2004. For comparison, silicon solar cells used up 33% of the world's electronic grade silicon production in 2006.

2.17.3 Gallium arsenide (GaAs) multijunction

High-efficiency multi junction cells were originally developed for special applications such as satellites and space exploration, but at present, their use in terrestrial concentrators might be the lowest cost alternative in terms of \$/kWh and \$/W. These multi junction cells consist of multiple thin films produced using Metalorganic vapour phase epitaxy. A triple-junction cell, for example, may consist of the semiconductors: GaAs, Ge, and GaInP_2 . Each type of semiconductor will have a characteristic band gap energy which, loosely speaking, causes it to absorb light most efficiently at a certain color, or more precisely, to absorb electromagnetic radiation over a portion of the spectrum. The semiconductors are carefully chosen to absorb nearly the entire solar spectrum, thus generating electricity from as much of the solar energy as possible.

GaAs based multi junction devices are the most efficient solar cells to date, reaching a record high of 40.7% efficiency under solar concentration and laboratory conditions.

This technology is currently being utilized in the Mars rover missions.

Tandem solar cells based on monolithic, series connected, gallium indium phosphide (GaInP), gallium arsenide GaAs, and germanium Ge pn junctions, are seeing demand rapidly rise. In just the past 12 months (12/2006 - 12/2007), the cost of 4N gallium metal has risen from about \$350 per kg to \$680 per kg. Additionally, germanium metal prices have risen substantially to \$1000–\$1200 per kg this year. Those materials include gallium (4N, 6N and 7N Ga), arsenic (4N, 6N

and 7N) and germanium, pyrolytic boron nitride (pBN) crucibles for growing crystals, and boron oxide, these products are critical to the entire substrate manufacturing industry.

Triple-junction GaAs solar cells were also being used as the power source of the Dutch four-time World Solar Challenge winners Nuna in 2005 and 2007, and also by the Dutch solar cars Solutra (2005) and Twente One (2007).

The Dutch Radboud University Nijmegen set the record for thin film solar cell efficiency using a single junction GaAs to 25.8% in August 2008 using only 4 μm thick GaAs layer which can be transferred from a wafer base to glass or plastic film.

2.17.4 Light-absorbing dyes (DSSC)

Typically a ruthenium metal organic dye (Ru-centered) is used as a monolayer of light-absorbing material. The dye-sensitized solar cell depends on a meso porous layer of nano particulate titanium dioxide to greatly amplify the surface area (200-300 m^2/g TiO_2 , as compared to approximately 10 m^2/g of flat single crystal). The photo generated electrons from the *light absorbing dye* are passed on to the *n-type* TiO_2 , and the holes are passed to an electrolyte on the other side of the dye. The circuit is completed by a redox couple in the electrolyte, which can be liquid or solid. This type of cell allows a more flexible use of materials, and is typically manufactured by screen printing and/or use of Ultrasonic Nozzles, with the potential for lower processing costs than those used for *bulk* solar cells. However, the dyes in these cells also suffer from degradation under heat and UV light, and the cell casing is difficult to seal due to the solvents used in assembly. In spite of the above, this is a popular emerging technology with some commercial impact forecast within this decade.

2.17.5 Organic/polymer solar cells

Organic solar cells and Polymer solar cells are built from thin films (typically 100 nm) of organic semiconductors such as polymers and small-molecule compounds like polyphenylene vinylene, copper phthalocyanine (a blue or green organic pigment) and carbon fullerenes and fullerene derivatives such as PCBM. Energy conversion efficiencies achieved to date using conductive polymers are low compared to inorganic materials, with the highest reported efficiency of 6.5% for a tandem cell architecture. However, these cells could be beneficial for some applications where mechanical flexibility and disposability are important.

These devices differ from inorganic semiconductor solar cells in that they do not rely on the large built-in electric field of a PN junction to separate the electrons and holes created when photons are absorbed. The active region of an organic device consists of two materials, one which acts as an electron donor and the other as an acceptor. When a photon is converted into an electron hole pair, typically in the donor material, the charges tend to remain bound in the form of an exciton, and are separated when the exciton diffuses to the donor-acceptor interface. The short exciton diffusion lengths of most polymer systems tend to limit the efficiency of such devices. Nano structured interfaces, sometimes in the form of bulk hetero junctions, can improve performance.

2.17.6 Silicon Thin Films

Silicon thin-film cells are mainly deposited by chemical vapor deposition (typically plasma-enhanced (PE-CVD)) from silane gas and hydrogen gas. Depending on the deposition parameters, this can yield:

1. Amorphous silicon (a-Si or a-Si:H)
2. Proto crystalline silicon or
3. Nano crystalline silicon (nc-Si or nc-Si:H), also called microcrystalline silicon.

These types of silicon present dangling and twisted bonds, which results in deep defects (energy levels in the band gap) as well as deformation of the valence and conduction bands (band tails). The solar cells made from these materials tend to have lower *energy conversion efficiency* than *bulk* silicon, but are also less expensive to produce. The quantum efficiency of thin film solar cells is also lower due to reduced number of collected charge carriers per incident photon.

Amorphous silicon has a higher band gap (1.7 eV) than crystalline silicon (c-Si) (1.1 eV), which means it absorbs the visible part of the solar spectrum more strongly than the infrared portion of the spectrum. As **nc-Si** has about the same band gap as c-Si, the nc-Si and a-Si can advantageously be combined in thin layers, creating a layered cell called a **tandem cell**. The top cell in a-Si absorbs the visible light and leaves the infrared part of the spectrum for the bottom cell in nano crystalline Si.

Recently, solutions to overcome the limitations of thin-film crystalline silicon have been developed. Light trapping schemes where the weakly absorbed long wavelength light is obliquely coupled into the silicon and traverses the film several times can significantly enhance the absorption of sunlight in the thin silicon films. Thermal processing techniques can significantly enhance the crystal quality of the silicon and thereby lead to higher efficiencies of the final solar cells.

A silicon thin film technology is being developed for building integrated photo voltaics (BIPV) in the form of semi-transparent solar cells which can be applied as window glazing. These cells function as window tinting while generating electricity.

2.17.7 Nano crystalline solar cells

These structures make use of some of the same thin-film light absorbing materials but are overlain as an extremely thin absorber on a supporting matrix of conductive polymer or meso porous metal oxide having a very high surface area to increase internal reflections (and hence increase the probability of light absorption). Using nano crystals allows one to design architectures on the length scale of nanometers, the typical exciton diffusion length. In particular, single-nano crystal ('channel') devices, an array of single p-n junctions between the electrodes and separated by a period of about a diffusion length, represent a new architecture for solar cells and potentially high efficiency.

2.18 Concentrating photovoltaic's (CPV)

Concentrating photovoltaic systems use a large area of lenses or mirrors to focus sunlight on a small area of photovoltaic cells. If these systems use single or dual-axis tracking to improve performance, they may be referred to as *Heliostat Concentrator Photovoltaic's* (HCPV). The primary attraction of CPV systems is their reduced usage of semiconducting material which is expensive and currently in short supply. Additionally, increasing the concentration ratio improves the performance of general photovoltaic materials. Despite the advantages of CPV technologies their application has been limited by the costs of focusing, tracking and cooling equipment. On October 25, 2006, the Australian federal government and the Victorian state government together with photovoltaic technology company Solar Systems announced a project using this technology, solar power station in Victoria, planned to come online in 2008 and be completed by 2013. This plant, at 154 MW, would be ten times larger than the largest current photovoltaic plant in the world.

2.19 Silicon solar cell device manufacture

Because solar cells are semiconductor devices, they share many of the same processing and manufacturing techniques as other semiconductor devices such as computer and memory chips. However, the stringent requirements for cleanliness and quality control of semiconductor fabrication are a little more relaxed for solar cells. Most large-scale commercial solar cell factories today make screen printed poly-crystalline silicon solar cells. Single crystalline wafers which are used in the semiconductor industry can be made into excellent high efficiency solar cells, but they are generally considered to be too expensive for large-scale mass production.

Poly-crystalline silicon wafers are made by wire-sawing block-cast silicon ingots into very thin (180 to 350 micrometer) slices or wafers. The wafers are usually lightly p-type doped. To make a solar cell from the wafer, a surface diffusion of n-type dopants is performed on the front side of the wafer. This forms a p-n junction a few hundred nanometers below the surface.

Figure 23. Solar powered scientific calculator

Antireflection coatings, which increase the amount of light coupled into the solar cell, are typically next applied. Over the past decade, silicon nitride has gradually replaced titanium dioxide as the antireflection coating of choice because of its excellent surface passivation qualities (i.e., it prevents carrier recombination at the surface of the solar cell). It is typically applied in a layer several hundred nanometers thick using plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD). Some solar cells have textured front surfaces that, like antireflection coatings, serve to increase the amount of light coupled into the cell. Such surfaces can usually only be formed on single-crystal silicon, though in recent years methods of forming them on multi crystalline silicon have been developed.

The wafer then has a full area metal contact made on the back surface, and a grid-like metal contact made up of fine "fingers" and larger "bus bars" are screen-printed onto the front surface using a silver paste. The rear contact is also formed by screen-printing a metal paste, typically aluminum. Usually this contact covers the entire rear side of the cell, though in some cell designs it is printed in a grid pattern. The paste is then fired at several hundred degrees Celsius to form metal electrodes in ohmic contact with the silicon. After the metal contacts are made, the solar cells are interconnected in series (and/or parallel) by flat wires or metal ribbons, and assembled into modules or "solar panels". Solar panels have a sheet of tempered glass on the front, and a polymer encapsulation on the back. Tempered glass cannot be used with amorphous silicon cells because of the high temperatures during the deposition process.

2.20 Lifespan

Most commercially available solar cells are capable of producing electricity for at least twenty years without a significant decrease in efficiency.

2.21 Costs

Cost is established in cost-per-watt and in cost-per-watt in 24 hours for infrared capable photovoltaic cells.

2.21.1 Slicing costs

University of Utah engineers devised a new way to slice thin wafers of the chemical element germanium for use in the most efficient type of solar power cells. The new method should lower the cost of such cells by reducing the waste and breakage of the brittle semiconductor.

2.21.2 Low Cost Solar Cell

Dye-sensitized solar cell and Luminescent solar concentrators are considered low-cost solar cells.

These cells is extremely promising because it is made of low-cost materials and does not need elaborate apparatus to manufacture, so it can be made in a DIY way allowing more players to produce it than any other type of solar cell. In bulk it should be significantly less expensive than older solid-state cell designs. It can be engineered into flexible sheets. Although its conversion efficiency is less than the best thin film cells, its price/performance ratio should be high enough to allow them to compete with fossil fuel electrical generation.

2.22 Current research on materials and devices

There are currently many research groups active in the field of photovoltaics in universities and research institutions around the world. This research can be divided into three areas: making current technology solar cells cheaper and/or more efficient to effectively compete with other

energy sources; developing new technologies based on new solar cell architectural designs; and developing new materials to serve as light absorbers and charge carriers.

2.23 Silicon processing

One way of reducing the cost is to develop cheaper methods of obtaining silicon that is sufficiently pure. Silicon is a very common element, but is normally bound in silica, or silica sand. Processing silica (SiO_2) to produce silicon is a very high energy process - at current efficiencies, it takes one to two years for a conventional solar cell to generate as much energy as was used to make the silicon it contains. More energy efficient methods of synthesis are not only beneficial to the solar industry, but also to industries surrounding silicon technology as a whole.

The current industrial production of silicon is via the reaction between carbon (charcoal) and silica at a temperature around 1700 degrees Celsius. In this process, known as carbothermic reduction, each ton of silicon (metallurgical grade, about 98% pure) is produced with the emission of about 1.5 tons of carbon dioxide.

Solid silica can be directly converted (reduced) to pure silicon by electrolysis in a molten salt bath at a fairly mild temperature (800 to 900 degrees Celsius). While this new process is in principle the same as the FFC Cambridge Process which was first discovered in late 1996, the interesting laboratory finding is that such electrolytic silicon is in the form of porous silicon which turns readily into a fine powder, (with a particle size of a few micrometers), and may therefore offer new opportunities for development of solar cell technologies.

Another approach is also to reduce the amount of silicon used and thus cost, is by micromachining wafers into very thin, virtually transparent layers that could be used as transparent architectural coverings. The technique involves taking a silicon wafer, typically 1 to 2 mm thick, and making a multitude of parallel, transverse slices across the wafer, creating a large number of slivers that have a thickness of 50 micrometers and a width equal to the thickness of the original wafer. These slices are rotated 90 degrees, so that the surfaces corresponding to the faces of the original wafer become the edges of the slivers. The result is to convert, for example, a 150 mm diameter, 2 mm-thick wafer having an exposed silicon surface area of about 175 cm^2 per side into about 1000 slivers having dimensions of $100 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm} \times 0.1 \text{ mm}$, yielding a total exposed silicon surface area of about 2000 cm^2 per side. As a result of this rotation, the electrical doping and contacts that were on the face of the wafer are located the edges of the sliver, rather than the front and rear as is the case with conventional wafer cells. This has the interesting effect of making the cell sensitive from both the front and rear of the cell (a property known as bifaciality). Using this technique, one silicon wafer is enough to build a 140 watt panel, compared to about 60 wafers needed for conventional modules of same power output.

2.24 Thin-film processing

Thin-film photovoltaic cells can use less than 1% of the expensive raw material (silicon or other light absorbers) compared to wafer based solar cells, leading to a significant price drop per Watt peak capacity. There are many research groups around the world actively researching different

thin-film approaches and/or materials. However, it remains to be seen if these solutions can achieve a similar market penetration as traditional bulk silicon solar modules.

One particularly promising technology is crystalline silicon thin films on glass substrates. This technology combines the advantages of crystalline silicon as a solar cell material (abundance, non-toxicity, high efficiency, long-term stability) with the cost savings of using a thin-film approach.

Another interesting aspect of thin-film solar cells is the possibility to deposit the cells on all kind of materials, including flexible substrates (PET for example), which opens a new dimension for new applications.

2.25 Metamorphic Multi junction Solar Cell

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory won a R&D Magazine's R&D 100 Awards for its Metamorphic Multi junction Solar Cell, an ultra-light and flexible cell that converts solar energy with record efficiency.

The ultra-light, highly efficient solar cell was developed at NREL and is being commercialized by Emcore Corp. of Albuquerque, N.M., in partnership with the Air Force Research Laboratories Space Vehicles Directorate at Kirtland Air Force Base in Albuquerque.

It represents a new class of solar cells with clear advantages in performance, engineering design, operation and cost. For decades, conventional cells have featured wafers of semiconducting materials with similar crystalline structure. Their performance and cost effectiveness is constrained by growing the cells in an upright configuration. Meanwhile, the cells are rigid, heavy and thick with a bottom layer made of germanium.

In the new method, the cell is grown upside down. These layers use high-energy materials with extremely high quality crystals, especially in the upper layers of the cell where most of the power is produced. Not all of the layers follow the lattice pattern of even atomic spacing. Instead, the cell includes a full range of atomic spacing, which allows for greater absorption and use of sunlight. The thick, rigid germanium layer is removed, reducing the cell's cost and 94% of its weight. By turning the conventional approach to cells on its head, the result is an ultra-light and flexible cell that also converts solar energy with record efficiency (40.8 percent under 326 suns concentration).

2.26 Polymer processing

The invention of conductive polymers (for which Alan Heeger, Alan G. MacDiarmid and Hideki Shirakawa were awarded a Nobel Prize) may lead to the development of much cheaper cells that are based on inexpensive plastics. However, organic solar cells generally suffer from degradation upon exposure to UV light, and hence have lifetimes which are far too short to be viable. The bonds in the polymers, are always susceptible to breaking up when radiated with shorter wavelengths. Additionally, the conjugated double bond systems in the polymers which carry the charge react more readily with light and oxygen. So most conductive polymers being highly

unsaturated and reactive are highly sensitive to atmospheric moisture and oxidation, making commercial applications difficult.

2.27 Nano particle processing

Experimental non-silicon solar panels can be made of quantum hetero structures, e.g. Carbon nano tubes or quantum dots, embedded in conductive polymers or meso porous metal oxides. In addition, thin films of many of these materials on conventional silicon solar cells can increase the optical coupling efficiency into the silicon cell, thus boosting the overall efficiency. By varying the size of the quantum dots, the cells can be tuned to absorb different wavelengths. Although the research is still in its infancy, quantum dot-modified photovoltaics may be able to achieve up to 42 percent energy conversion efficiency due to multiple exciton generation (MEG).

Researchers located at the University of California, San Diego have come up with a way of making solar photovoltaic cells more efficient by making them fuzzy with indium phosphide nano wires. It sounds similar to a project announced by a consortium of German universities, working in concert with Harvard University Science department.

2.28 Transparent conductors

Many new solar cells use transparent thin films that are also conductors of electrical charge. The dominant conductive thin films used in research now are transparent conductive oxides (abbreviated "TCO"), and include fluorine-doped tin oxide ($\text{SnO}_2:\text{F}$, or "FTO"), doped zinc oxide (e.g.: $\text{ZnO}:\text{Al}$), and indium tin oxide (abbreviated "ITO"). These conductive films are also used in the LCD industry for flat panel displays. The dual function of a TCO allows light to pass through a substrate window to the active light absorbing material beneath, and also serves as an ohmic contact to transport photo generated charge carriers away from that light absorbing material. The present TCO materials are effective for research, but perhaps are not yet optimized for large-scale photovoltaic production. They require very special deposition conditions at high vacuum, they can sometimes suffer from poor mechanical strength, and most have poor transmittance in the infrared portion of the spectrum (e.g.: ITO thin films can also be used as infrared filters in airplane windows). These factors make large-scale manufacturing more costly.

A relatively new area has emerged using carbon nano tube networks as a transparent conductor for organic solar cells. Nano tube networks are flexible and can be deposited on surfaces a variety of ways. With some treatment, nano tube films can be highly transparent in the infrared, possibly enabling efficient low band gap solar cells. Nano tube networks are p-type conductors, whereas traditional transparent conductors are exclusively n-type. The availability of a p-type transparent conductor could lead to new cell designs that simplify manufacturing and improve efficiency.

2.29 Silicon wafer based solar cells

Despite the numerous attempts at making better solar cells by using new and exotic materials, the reality is that the photovoltaic market is still dominated by silicon wafer-based solar cells (first-generation solar cells). This means that most solar cell manufacturers are currently equipped to

produce this type of solar cells. Consequently, a large body of research is being done all over the world to manufacture silicon wafer-based solar cells at lower cost and to increase the conversion efficiencies without an exorbitant increase in production cost. The ultimate goal for both wafer based and alternative photovoltaic concepts is to produce solar electricity at a cost comparable to currently marked dominating technologies like coal and nuclear power in order to make it the leading primary energy source. To achieve this it may be necessary to reduce the cost of installed solar systems from currently about US\$ 1.80 (for bulk Si technologies) to about US\$ 0.50 per Watt peak power. Since a major part of the final cost of a traditional bulk silicon module is related to the high cost of solar grade poly silicon feedstock (about US\$ 0.4/Watt peak) there exists substantial drive to make Si solar cells thinner (material savings) or to make solar cells from cheaper upgraded metallurgical silicon.

IBM has a semiconductor wafer reclamation process that uses a specialized pattern removal technique to repurpose scrap semiconductor wafers to a form used to manufacture silicon-based solar panels. The new process was recently awarded the "2007 Most Valuable Pollution Prevention Award" from The National Pollution Prevention Roundtable (NPPR).

2.30 Infrared solar cells

Researchers at Idaho National Laboratory, along with partners at Micro continuum Inc. (Cambridge, MA) and Patrick Pinhero of the University of Missouri, have devised an inexpensive way to produce plastic sheets containing billions of nano antennas that collect heat energy generated by the sun and other sources, which garnered two 2007 Nano50 awards. The technology is the first step toward a solar energy collector that could be mass-produced on flexible materials. While methods to convert the energy into usable electricity still need to be developed, the sheets could one day be manufactured as lightweight "skins" that power everything from hybrid cars to computers and iPods with higher efficiency than traditional solar cells. The nano antennas also have the potential to act as cooling devices that draw waste heat from buildings or electronics without using electricity. The nano antennas target mid-infrared rays, which the Earth continuously radiates as heat after absorbing energy from the sun during the day; also double-sided nano antenna sheets can harvest energy from different parts of the sun's spectrum. In contrast, traditional solar cells can only use visible light, rendering them idle after dark.

Also Konarka is researching infrared light activated photovoltaic's which would enable night-time power generation.

2.31 UV Solar cells

Japan's National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) has succeeded in developing a transparent solar cell that uses ultraviolet light to generate electricity but allows visible light to pass through it. Most conventional solar cells use visible and infrared light to generate electricity. In contrast, the innovative new solar cell uses ultraviolet radiation. used to replace conventional window glass, the installation surface area could be large, leading to potential uses that take advantage of the combined functions of power generation, lighting and temperature control.

Also PEDOT-PSS solar cells is a ultraviolet (UV) light selective and sensitive photovoltaic cell easily fabricated.

2.32 3-D solar cells

Three-dimensional solar cells that capture nearly all of the light that strikes them and could boost the efficiency of photovoltaic (PV) systems while reducing their size, weight and mechanical complexity. The new 3D solar cells capture photons from sunlight using an array of miniature “tower” structures that resemble high-rise buildings in a city street grid.

2.33 Antireflective and all-angle coating

With a reflective coating, developed at RPI, the material absorbs 96.21 per cent of incident sunlight. This gain in absorption was consistent across the entire spectrum of sunlight, from UV to visible light and infrared.

Such a method tackles the problem of absorbing sunlight evenly and equally from all angles. The seven layers, each with a height of 50-100 nm, are made up of silicon dioxide and titanium dioxide nano rods positioned at an oblique angle. Each layer looks and functions similar to a dense forest where sunlight is "captured" between the trees. The nano rods were attached to a silicon substrate via chemical vapor disposition and the new coating can be affixed to nearly any photovoltaic materials for use in solar cells, including III-V multi-junction and cadmium telluride.

2.34 Meta materials

Researchers at Duke University and Boston College have engineered a meta material that utilizes tiny geometric shapes to absorb both the electrical and magnetic properties of electromagnetic waves over a certain frequency range at a level that meets standards of scientific perfection. This results in the total absorption of light, turning it into heat, which can then create energy.

2.35 Photovoltaic thermal hybrid

Systems which combine Photovoltaic with thermal solar, the advantage of such a system is that the thermal solar part carries heat away and cools the PV cells, keeping temperature down lowers the resistance and improves the PV cell's efficiency.

2.36 Validation, Certification and Manufacturers

National Renewable Energy Laboratory tests and validates solar technologies.

There are three reliable certifications of solar equipment: UL and IEEE (both U.S. standards) and IEC.

Solar cells are manufactured primarily in Japan, China, Germany, Taiwan and the USA, though numerous other nations have or are acquiring significant solar cell production capacity. While technologies are constantly evolving toward higher efficiencies, the most effective cells for low cost electrical production are not necessarily those with the highest efficiency, but those with a balance between low-cost production and efficiency high enough to minimize area-related balance of systems cost. Those companies with large scale manufacturing technology for coating inexpensive substrates may, in fact, ultimately be the lowest cost net electricity producers, even with cell efficiencies that are lower than those of single-crystal technologies.

2.37 Top Solar Cell Manufacturers by Market Cap

As of 22 April 2009, the top manufacturers by market capitalization in the Solar Cell industry are given below.

Company	Exchange	Ticker	Cap
Kyocera	NYSE	KYO	13.6B
First Solar	NASDAQ	FSLR	11.9B
Suntech Power Holdings	NYSE	STP	2.07B
Solar World AG	FRA	SWV	1.23B
Energy Conversion Devices	NASDAQ	ENER	750M
JA Solar Holdings	NASDAQ	JASO	492M
Evergreen Solar	NASDAQ	ESLR	358M

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3. A Solar Tracker

A **solar tracker** is a device for orienting a day lighting reflector, solar photovoltaic panel or concentrating solar reflector or lens toward the sun. The sun's position in the sky varies both with the seasons (elevation) and time of day as the sun moves across the sky. Solar powered equipment works best when pointed at or near the sun, so a solar tracker can increase the effectiveness of such equipment over any fixed position, at the cost of additional system complexity. There are many types of solar trackers, of varying costs, sophistication, and performance. One well-known type of solar tracker is the heliostat, a movable mirror that reflects the moving sun to a fixed location, but many other approaches are used as well.

The required accuracy of the solar tracker depends on the application. Concentrators, especially in solar cell applications, require a high degree of accuracy to ensure that the concentrated sunlight is directed precisely to the powered device, which is at (or near) the focal point of the reflector or lens. Typically concentrator systems will not work at all without tracking, so at least single-axis tracking is mandatory. Very large power plants or high temperature materials research facilities using multiple ground-mounted mirrors and an absorber target require very high precision similar to that used for solar telescopes. (See heliostat.)

Non-concentrating applications require less accuracy, and many work without any tracking at all. However, tracking can substantially improve both the amount of total power produced by a system and that produced during critical system demand periods. (typically late afternoon in hot climates) The use of trackers in non-concentrating applications is usually an engineering decision based on economics. Compared to photovoltaic, trackers can be inexpensive. This makes them especially effective for photovoltaic systems using high-efficiency (and thus expensive) panels.

For low-temperature solar thermal applications, trackers are not usually used, owing to the high expense of trackers compared to adding more collector area and the more restricted solar angles required for winter performance, which influence the average year-round system capacity.

3.1 Maintenance

Some solar trackers may operate most effectively with seasonal position adjustment and most will need inspection and lubrication on an annual basis. As most trackers are made from mild steel, maintenance of paint is typically required, and may be critical in highly corrosive environments, such as near saltwater or in polluted industrial localities. In regions with extended summer dry seasons the periodic washing of the panels may significantly increase performance at a critical demand time, particularly for grid-tied systems.

3.2 Tracker mount types

Solar trackers may be active or passive and may be single axis or dual axis. Single axis trackers usually use a polar mount for maximum solar efficiency. Single axis trackers will usually have a manual elevation (axis tilt) adjustment on a second axis which is adjusted on regular intervals throughout the year. Compared to a fixed mount, a single axis tracker increases annual output by

approximately 30% and a dual axis tracker an additional 6%. There are two types of dual axis trackers, polar and altitude-azimuth.

3.3 Polar

Polar trackers have one axis aligned to be roughly parallel to the axis of rotation of the earth around the north and south poles-- hence the name *polar*. (With telescopes, this is called an *equatorial mount*.) Single axis tracking is often used when combined with time-of-use metering, since strong afternoon performance is particularly desirable for grid-tied photovoltaic systems, as production at this time will match the peak demand time for summer season air-conditioning. A fixed system oriented to optimize this limited time performance will have a relatively low annual production. The polar axis should be angled towards due north, and the angle between this axis and the vertical should be equal to your latitude.

Figure 1. Single axis Sun Power T20 trackers, with roughly polar orientation, at Nellis Air Force Base, in Nevada, USA. The arrays form part of the Nellis Solar Power Plant and was designed and built by SunPower corporation. Credit: U.S. Air Force photo by Senior Airman Larry E. Reid Jr.

Simple polar trackers with single axis tracking may also have an adjustment along a second axis: the angle of *declination*. This allows you to angle the panel to face the sun when it is higher in the sky (and further northward) in the summer, and to face it lower in the sky (and further southward) in the winter. It might be set with manual or automated adjustments, depending on your polar-tracking device. If one is not planning on adjusting this angle of declination at all during the year, it is normally set to zero degrees, facing your panel straight out perpendicular to the polar axis, as that is where the mean path of the sun is found. Occasional or continuous adjustments to the declination compensate for the northward and southward shift in the sun's path through the sky as it moves through the seasons (and around the ecliptic) over the course of the year.

When the manual method is used for adjustment of the declination, it should be done at least twice a year: Once at the autumnal equinox to establish the best position for the winter, and a second adjustment on the vernal equinox, to optimize it for the summer. The sun's declination at the spring equinox is 0° . It moves up to 22.5° in the summer, then drifts back down through 0° at fall equinox, and down to -22.5° in the winter. So, for example, you might choose to set the declination at 15° or 20° as a reasonably optimal position for the summer months.

Such trackers may also be referred to as a "single-axis tracker", because only one drive mechanism is needed for daily operation. This reduces the system cost and allows the use of simpler tracking methods, including passive and chronological tracking (described below).

3.4 Horizontal axle

Several manufacturers can deliver single axis horizontal trackers which may be oriented by either passive or active mechanisms, depending upon manufacturer. In these, a long horizontal tube is supported on bearings mounted upon pylons or frames. The axis of the tube is on a North-South line. Panels are mounted upon the tube, and the tube will rotate on its axis to track the apparent motion of the sun through the day. Since these do not tilt toward the equator they are not especially effective during winter mid day (unless located near the equator), but add a substantial amount of productivity during the spring and summer seasons when the solar path is high in the sky. These devices are less effective at higher latitudes. The principal advantage is the inherent robustness of the supporting structure and the simplicity of the mechanism. Since the panels are horizontal, they can be compactly placed on the axle tube without danger of self-shading and are also readily accessible for cleaning. For active mechanisms, a single control and motor may be used to actuate multiple rows of panels. Manufacturers include Array Technologies, Inc. Wattsun Solar Trackers (gear driven active), Zomeworks (passive) and Power light (active).

Figure 2. Wattsun HZ-Series Linear Axis Tracker in South Korea. These trackers use a horizontal axis

3.5 Vertical axle

Figure 3. Gemini House rotates in its entirety and the solar panels rotate independently, allowing control of the natural heating from the sun. The inventor stands in the middle of the group

A single axis tracker may be constructed that pivots only about a vertical axle, with the panels either vertical, at a fixed, adjustable, or tracked elevation angle. Such trackers with fixed or (seasonably) adjustable angles are suitable for high latitudes, where the apparent solar path is not especially high, but which leads to long days in summer, with the sun traveling through a long arc. This method has been used in the construction of a cylindrical house in Austria (latitude above 45 degrees north) that rotates in its entirety to track the sun, with vertical panels mounted on one side of the building.

3.6 Altitude-azimuth

A type of mounting that supports the weight of the solar tracker and allows it to move in two directions to locate a specific target. One axis of support is horizontal (called the altitude) and allows the telescope to move up and down. The other axis is vertical (called the azimuth) and allows the telescope to swing in a circle parallel to the ground. This makes it easy to position the telescope: swing it around in a circle and then lift it to the target. However, tracking an object as the Earth turns is more complicated. The telescope needs to be adjusted in both directions while tracking, which requires a computer to control the telescope.

3.6.1 Two-axis mount

Restricted to active trackers, this mount is also becoming popular as a large telescope mount owing to its structural simplicity and compact dimensions. One axis is a vertical pivot shaft or horizontal ring mount that allows the device to be swung to a compass point. The second axis is a horizontal elevation pivot mounted upon the azimuth platform. By using combinations of the two axis, any location in the upward hemisphere may be pointed. Such systems may be operated under computer control according to the expected solar orientation, or may use a tracking sensor to control motor drives that orient the panels toward the sun. This type of mount is also used to orient parabolic reflectors that mount a Stirling engine to produce electricity at the device.

Figure 4. Point focus parabolic dish with Stirling system. The horizontally rotating azimuth table mounts the vertical frames on each side which hold the elevation trunions for the dish and its integral engine/generator mount.

3.6.2 Multi-mirror reflective unit

A recent development, this device uses multiple mirrors in a horizontal plane to reflect sunlight upward to a high temperature photovoltaic or other system requiring concentrated solar power. Structural problems and expense are greatly reduced since the mirrors are not significantly exposed to wind loads. Through the employment of a patented mechanism, only two drive systems are required for each device. Because of the configuration of the device it is especially suited for use on flat roofs and at lower latitudes. While limited commercial availability was expected in 2007 the company has removed the descriptive web page from their site and is now promoting a two-axis clustered fresnel lens device. The units illustrated each produce approximately 200 peak DC watts.

Figure 5. Energy Innovations test units

3.7 Drive types

Active trackers use motors and gear trains to direct the tracker as commanded by a controller responding to the solar direction.

Active two-axis trackers are also used to orient heliostats - movable mirrors that reflect sunlight toward the absorber of a central power station. As each mirror in a large field will have an individual orientation these are controlled programmatically through a central computer system, which also allows the system to be shut down when necessary.

Light-sensing trackers typically have two photo sensors, such as photodiodes, configured differentially so that they output a null when receiving the same light flux. Mechanically, they should be omni directional (i.e. flat) and are aimed 90 degrees apart. This will cause the steepest part of their cosine transfer functions to balance at the steepest part, which translates into maximum sensitivity.

Since the motors consume energy, one wants to use them only as necessary. So instead of a continuous motion, the heliostat is moved in discrete steps. Also, if the light is below some threshold there would not be enough power generated to warrant reorientation. This is also true when there is not enough difference in light level from one direction to another, such as when clouds are passing overhead. Consideration must be made to keep the tracker from wasting energy during cloudy periods.

Passive trackers use a low boiling point compressed gas fluid that is driven to one side or the other (by solar heat creating gas pressure) to cause the tracker to move in response to an imbalance. As this is a non-precision orientation it is unsuitable for certain types of concentrating photovoltaic collectors but works fine for common PV panel types. These will have viscous dampers to prevent excessive motion in response to wind gusts. Shader/reflectors are used to reflect early morning sunlight to "wake up" the panel and tilt it toward the sun, which can take nearly an hour. The time to do this can be greatly reduced by adding a self-releasing tiedown that positions the panel slightly past the zenith (so that the fluid does not have to overcome gravity) and using the tiedown in the evening. (A slack-pulling spring will prevent release in windy overnight conditions.)

Figure 6. Zomeworks passive tracker head in Spring/Summer tilt position with panels on light blue rack pivoted to morning position against stop. Dark blue objects are hydraulic dampers.

The term "passive tracker" is also used for photovoltaic modules that include a hologram behind stripes of photovoltaic cells. That way, sunlight passes through the transparent part of the module and reflects on the hologram. This allows sunlight to hit the cell from behind, thereby increasing the module's efficiency. Also, the module does not have to move since the hologram always reflects sunlight from the correct angle towards the cells.

3.8 Chronological tracker

A chronological tracker counteracts the Earth's rotation by turning at an equal rate as the earth, but in the opposite direction. Actually the rates aren't quite equal, because as the earth goes around the sun, the position of the sun changes with respect to the earth by 360° every year or 365.24 days. A chronological tracker is a very simple yet potentially a very accurate solar tracker specifically for use with a polar mount (see above). The drive method may be as simple as a gear motor that rotates at a very slow average rate of one revolution per day (15 degrees per hour). In theory the tracker may rotate completely, assuming there is enough clearance for a complete rotation, and assuming that twisting wires are not an issue, such as with a solar concentrator or the tracker may be reset each day to avoid these issues. Alternatively, an electronic controller may be used, with a real time clock that is used to infer the "solar time" (hour angle). Tracking adjustments can be made incrementally or continuously.

3.9 Thin-film solar tracker

The solar energy experts at Denver-based Co energy Americas and officials at California's South San Joaquin Irrigation District (SSJID) have installed what is believed to be the world's first single-axis solar tracking system featuring thin-film cells.

3.10 Optimum Orientation of Solar Panels

For best performance, PV systems aim to maximize the time they face the sun. Solar trackers aim to achieve this by moving PV panels to follow the sun. Static mounted systems can be optimized by analysis of the Sun path.

Advantages

- The 89 petawatts of sunlight reaching the Earth's surface is plentiful - almost 6,000 times more than the 15 terawatts of average power consumed by humans. Additionally, solar electric generation has the highest power density (global mean of 170 W/m²) among renewable energies.
- Solar power is pollution free during use. Production end wastes and emissions are manageable using existing pollution controls. End-of-use recycling technologies are under development.
- Facilities can operate with little maintenance or intervention after initial setup.
- Solar electric generation is economically superior where grid connection or fuel transport is difficult, costly or impossible. Examples include satellites, island communities, remote locations and ocean vessels.
- When grid-connected, solar electric generation can displace the highest cost electricity during times of peak demand (in most climatic regions), can reduce grid loading, and can eliminate the need for local battery power for use in times of darkness and high local demand; such application is enabled by net metering. Time-of-use net metering can be highly favorable, but requires newer electronic metering, and tends to be impractical for small users.
- Grid-connected solar electricity can be used locally thus reducing transmission/distribution losses (transmission losses were approximately 7.2% in 1995).
- Once the initial capital cost of building a solar power plant has been spent, operating costs are extremely low compared to existing power technologies.
- Compared to fossil and nuclear energy sources, very little research-money has been invested in the development of solar cells, so there is much room for improvement. Nevertheless, experimental high efficiency solar cells already have efficiencies of over 40% and efficiencies are rapidly rising while mass production costs are rapidly falling.

Disadvantages

- A major drawback is the sheer volume of land required to house a solar power generation plant. The 550MW California plant that is planned required 9.5 square miles. Many areas of the country could not find this amount of unused land or assemble the large number of parcels required for this type of project. At the same time, photovoltaics take up no land at all when installed on existing rooftops or on land not otherwise used, such as decommissioned coal pits or in deserts.
- Depending on the cost of the installation and local electric rates the payback can be 14–20 years. While the modules are warranted for 20 years, the investment is mostly lost if

you move. The city of Berkeley has come up with an innovative financing method to remove this limitation, by adding a tax assessment that is transferred with the home to pay for the solar panels.

- Solar electricity is more expensive based on current rates. Once a PV system is installed it will produce electricity for the same cost until the inverter needs replacing (about 12 years). Current utility rates have increased every year for the past 20 years and with the increasing pressure on carbon reduction the rate will increase more aggressively. This increase will (in the long run) easily offset the increased cost at installation but the timetable for payback is too long for most.
- Solar electricity is not available at night and is less available in cloudy weather conditions from conventional silicon based technologies. Therefore, a storage or complementary power system is required. However, the use of germanium in amorphous silicon-germanium thin film solar cells provides residual power generating capacity at night due to background infrared radiation. Fortunately, most power consumption is during the day, so solar does not need to be stored at all as long as it offsets peak and "shoulder" consumption.
- Limited power density: Average daily insolation in the contiguous U.S. is 3-7 Gigawatt-h/km² and on average lower in Europe.
- Solar cells produce DC which must be converted to AC (using a grid tie inverter) when used in currently existing distribution grids. This incurs an energy loss of 4-12%.

3.11 Applications

Power stations

Several large photovoltaic power plants were completed in Spain during 2008: the Parque Fotovoltaico Olmedilla de Alarcon (60 MW), Parque Solar Merida/Don Alvaro (30 MW), Planta solar Fuente Álamo (26 MW), Planta fotovoltaica de Lucainena de las Torres (23.2 MW), Parque Fotovoltaico Abertura Solar (23.1 MW), Parque Solar Hoya de Los Vincentes (23 MW), the Solarpark Calveron (21 MW), and the Planta Solar La Magascona (20 MW).

Figure7.Solar array at Nellis Air Force Base. These panels track the sun in one axis

The 14 MW Nellis Solar Power Plant is the largest solar photovoltaic system in North America, and is located within Nellis Air Force Base in Clark County, Nevada, on the northeast side of Las Vegas. The Nellis solar energy system will generate in excess of 25 million kilowatt-hours of electricity annually and supply more than 25 percent of the power used at the base.

In buildings

Building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) are increasingly incorporated into new domestic and industrial buildings as a principal or ancillary source of electrical power, and are one of the fastest growing segments of the photovoltaic industry. Typically, an array is incorporated into the roof or walls of a building and roof tiles with integrated PV cells can now be purchased. Arrays can also be retrofitted into existing buildings; in this case they are usually fitted on top of the existing roof structure. Alternatively, an array can be located separately from the building but connected by cable to supply power for the building.

Figure 8. Photovoltaic solar panels on a house roof.

Where a building is at a considerable distance from the public electricity supply (or grid) - in remote or mountainous areas - PV may be the preferred possibility for generating electricity, or PV may be used together with wind, diesel generators and/or hydroelectric power. In such off-grid circumstances batteries are usually used to store the electric power.

In locations near the grid, however, feeding the grid using PV panels is more practical, and leads to optimum use of the investment in the photovoltaic system. This requires both regulatory and commercial preparation, including net-metering and feed-in agreements. To provide for possible power failure, some grid tied systems are set up to allow local use disconnected from the grid. Most photovoltaics are grid connected. In the event the grid fails, the local system must not feed the grid to prevent the possible creation of dangerous islanding.

The power output of photovoltaic systems for installation in buildings is usually described in kilowatt-peak units (kWp).

In transport

PV has traditionally been used for auxiliary power in space. PV is rarely used to provide motive power in transport applications, but is being used increasingly to provide auxiliary power in boats and cars. Recent advances in solar race cars, however, have produced cars that with little changes could be used for transportation.

Rural electrification

Developing countries where many villages are often more than five kilometers away from grid power have begun using photovoltaics. In remote locations in India a rural lighting program has been providing solar powered LED lighting to replace kerosene lamps. The solar powered lamps were sold at about the cost of a few month's supply of kerosene. Cuba is working to provide solar power for areas that are off grid. These are areas where the social costs and benefits offer an excellent case for going solar though the lack of profitability could relegate such endeavors to humanitarian goals.

Solar roadways

A 45 mi (72 km) section of roadway in Idaho is being used to test the possibility of installing solar panels into the road surface, as roads are generally unobstructed to the sun and represent about the percentage of land area needed to replace other energy sources with solar power.

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4. Electrolysis

In chemistry and manufacturing, **electrolysis** is a method of using an electric current to drive an otherwise non-spontaneous chemical reaction. Electrolysis is commercially highly important as a stage in the separation of elements from naturally-occurring sources such as ores using an electrolytic cell.

4.1 History

- 1800 - William Nicholson and Johann Ritter decomposed water into hydrogen and oxygen.
- 1807 - Potassium, Sodium, Barium, Calcium and Magnesium were discovered by Sir Humphry Davy using electrolysis. ^[1]
- 1886 - Fluorine was discovered by Henri Moissan using electrolysis.
- 1886 - Hall-Héroult process developed for making aluminum
- 1890 - Castner-Kellner process developed for making sodium hydroxide

4.2 Overview

Electrolysis is the passage of an electric current through an ionic substance that is either molten or dissolved in a suitable solvent, resulting in chemical reactions at the electrodes and separation of materials.

The main components required to achieve electrolysis are:

- A liquid containing mobile ions - an electrolyte
- An external source of direct electric current
- Two solid rods or plates known as electrodes

The components perform the following roles in the electrolysis process:

- The mobile ions are the carriers of electrical current in the liquid (electrolyte). If the ions are not mobile, as in a solid salt then electrolysis cannot occur.
- The externally supplied direct electric current supplies the energy necessary to create or discharge the ions in the liquid or solution. Electric current is carried by electrons in the external circuit.
- The electrodes provide the physical interface between
 - The electrical circuit providing the energy to achieve the electrolysis
 - The electrolyte containing the ionic materials that are to be separated.

The electrodes must be able to conduct electricity. Electrodes of metal, graphite and semiconductor material are widely used. Choice of suitable electrode depends on:

- Chemical reactivity between the electrode and electrolyte
- Cost of manufacture of the electrode

Ancillary practical components to achieve electrolysis include:

- Vessels to supply, contain and remove the reactants and products
- Electrical circuitry

4.3 Process of electrolysis

The key process of electrolysis is the interchange of atoms and ions by the removal or addition of electrons from the external circuit. The required products of electrolysis are in some different physical state from the electrolyte and can be removed by some physical process. For example, in the electrolysis of brine to produce hydrogen and chlorine, the products are gaseous. These gaseous products bubble from the electrolyte and are collected.

A liquid containing mobile ions (electrolyte) is produced by

- Reaction of an ionic compound with a solvent (such as an acid) to produce mobile ions
- An ionic compound is melted (*fused*) by heating

An electrical potential is applied across a pair of electrodes immersed in the electrolyte.

Each electrode attracts ions that are of the opposite charge. Positively-charged ions (cations) move towards the electron-providing (negative) cathode, whereas negatively-charged ions (anions) move towards the positive anode.

At the electrodes, electrons are absorbed or released by the atoms and ions. Those atoms that gain or lose electrons to become charged ions pass into the electrolyte. Those ions that gain or lose electrons to become uncharged atoms separate from the electrolyte. The formation of uncharged atoms from ions is called discharging.

The energy required to cause the ions to migrate to the electrodes, and the energy to cause the change in ionic state, is provided by the external source of electrical potential.

4.4 Oxidation and reduction at the electrodes

Oxidation of ions or neutral molecules occurs at the anode, and the reduction of ions or neutral molecules occurs at the cathode. For example, it is possible to oxidize ferrous ions to ferric ions at the anode:

It is also possible to reduce ferricyanide ions to ferrocyanide ions at the cathode:

Neutral molecules can also react at either electrode. For example: p-Benzoquinone can be reduced to hydroquinone at the cathode:

In the last example, H^{+} ions (hydrogen ions) also take part in the reaction, and are provided by an acid in the solution, or the solvent itself (water, methanol etc). Electrolysis reactions involving H^{+} ions are fairly common in acidic solutions. In alkaline solutions, reactions involving OH^{-} (hydroxide ions) are common.

The substances oxidised or reduced can also be the solvent (usually water) or the electrodes. It is possible to have electrolysis involving gases.

4.5 Energy changes during electrolysis

The amount of electrical energy that must be added equals the change in Gibbs free energy of the reaction plus the losses in the system. The losses can (in theory) be arbitrarily close to zero, so the maximum thermodynamic efficiency equals the enthalpy change divided by the free energy change of the reaction. In most cases, the electric input is larger than the enthalpy change of the reaction, so some energy is released in the form of heat. In some cases, for instance, in the electrolysis of steam into hydrogen and oxygen at high temperature, the opposite is true. Heat is absorbed from the surroundings, and the heating value of the produced hydrogen is higher than the electric input.

Related techniques

The following techniques are related to electrolysis:

- Gel electrophoresis is an electrolysis using a gel solvent. It is used to separate substances, such as DNA strands, based on their electrical charge.
- Electrochemical cells, including the hydrogen fuel cell, utilize differences in Standard electrode potential in order to generate an electrical potential from which useful power can be extracted. Although related via the interaction of ions and electrodes, electrolysis and the operation of electrochemical cells are quite distinct. A chemical cell should **not** be thought of as performing "electrolysis in reverse".

4.6 Faraday's laws of electrolysis

4.6.1 First law of electrolysis

In 1832, Michael Faraday reported that the quantity of elements separated by passing an electrical current through a molten or dissolved salt is proportional to the quantity of electric charge passed through the circuit. This became the basis of the first law of electrolysis:

$$m = k \cdot q$$

4.6.2 Second law of electrolysis

Faraday also discovered that the mass of the resulting separated elements is directly proportional to the atomic masses of the elements when an appropriate integral divisor is applied. This provided strong evidence that discrete particles of matter exist as parts of the atoms of elements.

4.7 Industrial uses

- Production of aluminum, lithium, sodium, potassium, magnesium
- Coulometric techniques can be used to determine the amount of matter transformed during electrolysis by measuring the amount of electricity required to perform the electrolysis
- Production of chlorine and sodium hydroxide
- Production of sodium chlorate and potassium chlorate
- Production of per fluorinated organic compounds such as trifluoroacetic acid
- Production of electrolytic copper as a cathode, from refined copper of lower purity as an anode.

Figure 1. Hall-Heroult process for producing aluminum

Electrolysis has many other uses:

- Electrometallurgy is the process of reduction of metals from metallic compounds to obtain the pure form of metal using electrolysis. For example, sodium hydroxide in its molten form is separated by electrolysis into sodium and oxygen, both of which have important chemical uses. (Water is produced at the same time.)
- Anodization is an electrolytic process that makes the surface of metals resistant to corrosion. For example, ships are saved from being corroded by oxygen in the water by this process. The process is also used to decorate surfaces.
- A battery works by the reverse process to electrolysis. Humphry Davy found that lithium acts as an electrolyte and provides electrical energy.
- Production of oxygen for spacecraft and nuclear submarines.
- Electroplating is used in layering metals to fortify them. Electroplating is used in many industries for functional or decorative purposes, as in vehicle bodies and nickel coins.
- Production of hydrogen for fuel, using a cheap source of electrical energy.
- Electrolytic Etching of metal surfaces like tools or knives with a permanent mark or logo.

Electrolysis is also used in the cleaning and preservation of old artifacts. Because the process separates the non-metallic particles from the metallic ones, it is very useful for cleaning old coins and even larger objects.

4.8 Competing half-reactions in solution electrolysis

Using a cell containing inert platinum electrodes, electrolysis of aqueous solutions of some salts leads to reduction of the cations (e.g. metal deposition with e.g. zinc salts) and oxidation of the anions (e.g. evolution of bromine with bromides). However with salts of some metals (e.g. sodium) hydrogen is evolved at the cathode and for salts containing some anions (e.g. sulfate (SO_4^{2-})) oxygen is evolved at the anode, and in both cases this is due to water being reduced to form hydrogen or oxidized to form oxygen. In principle the voltage required to electrolyze a salt solution can be derived from the standard electrode potential for the reactions at the anode and cathode. The standard electrode potential is directly related to the Gibb's free energy, ΔG , for the reactions at each electrode and refers to an electrode with no current flowing.

4.9 Electrolysis of water

One important use of electrolysis of water is to produce hydrogen.

Hydrogen can be used as a fuel for powering internal combustion engines by combustion or electric motors via hydrogen fuel cells. This has been suggested as one approach to shift economies of the world from the current state of almost complete dependence upon hydrocarbons for energy.

Electrolysis of water can be observed by passing direct current from a battery or other DC power supply through a cup of water (in practice a salt water solution increases the reaction intensity making it easier to observe). Using platinum electrodes, hydrogen gas will be seen to bubble up at the cathode, and oxygen will bubble at the anode. If other metals are used as the anode, there is a chance that the oxygen will react with the anode instead of being released as a gas, or that the anode will dissolve. For example, using iron electrodes in a sodium chloride solution electrolyte, iron oxides will be produced at the anode. With zinc electrodes in a sodium chloride electrolyte, the anode will dissolve, producing zinc ions (Zn^{2+}) in the solution, and no oxygen will be formed. When producing large quantities of hydrogen, the use of reactive metal electrodes can significantly contaminate the electrolytic cell - which is why iron electrodes are not usually used for commercial electrolysis. Electrodes made of stainless steel can be used because they will not react with the oxygen.

The energy efficiency of water electrolysis varies widely. The efficiency is a measure of what fraction of electrical energy used is actually contained within the hydrogen. Some of the electrical energy is converted to heat, a useless by-product. Some reports quote efficiencies between 50% and 70% this efficiency is based on the Lower Heating Value of Hydrogen. The Lower Heating Value of Hydrogen is total thermal energy released when hydrogen is combusted minus the latent heat of vaporization of the water. This does not represent the total amount of energy within the hydrogen; hence the efficiency is lower than a more strict definition. Other reports quote the theoretical maximum efficiency of electrolysis as being between 80% and 94%. The theoretical maximum considers the total amount of energy absorbed by both the hydrogen

and oxygen. These values refer only to the efficiency of converting electrical energy into hydrogen's chemical energy. The energy lost in generating the electricity is not included. For instance, when considering a power plant that converts the heat of nuclear reactions into hydrogen via electrolysis, the total efficiency is more likely to be between 25% and 40%.

NREL found that a kilogram of hydrogen (roughly equivalent to a gallon of gasoline) could be produced by wind powered electrolysis for between \$5.55 in the near term and \$2.27 in the long term.

About four percent of hydrogen gas produced worldwide is created by electrolysis, and normally used onsite. Hydrogen is used for the creation of ammonia for fertilizer via the Haber process, and converting heavy petroleum sources to lighter fractions via hydro cracking.

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